

Complementary socio-economic impact analysis of the lepton collider-based research infrastructure.

Updated assumptions, input data, results and
calculations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document summarises the progress made to date on the assignment “[Updating and Expanding the Analysis of the Socio-Economic Impacts of the FCC-ee lepton collider](#)”¹. Findings from this assignment are expected to contribute to the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update, due by the end of February 2025.

The tables below summarise [preliminary results](#) from the quantitative assessment of socio-economic costs and benefits identified for the current design of FCC-ee. These results rely on data and information provided by CERN (to date) and are presented in the form of [two scenarios](#).

- The [Baseline Scenario](#) (Table 1) adopts a precautionary approach. It includes only the most certain costs and benefits. Therefore, it excludes some (local and environmental) benefits related to heat recovery, the value of emergency services, and the provision of incremental capacity of generation of clean electricity to society, as these benefits depend on commitments that may or may not materialise. The baseline scenario does not include the residual value of FCC-ee since the decision of building FCC-hh cannot be taken for granted at this stage. The dismantling costs for FCC-ee are instead considered in this scenario as a conservative estimate of decommissioning costs, for which no precise estimation is currently available. Decommissioning costs would incur in a scenario without FCC-hh to ensure the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure. Overall, the baseline scenario yields a positive net present value (discounted benefits minus discounted costs) of approximately [4 billion CHF](#), with a [benefit-cost ratio of 1.20](#)—indicating that benefits exceed costs by 20% over the entire lifecycle (2024–2064).
- The [Extended Scenario](#) (Table 2) is based on the assumption that the FCC-hh will be built. It incorporates dismantling costs for FCC-ee (necessary to host the FCC-hh subsequent project in the same tunnel) as well as additional benefits, including the residual value of remaining assets and some additional non-core elements. As shown in the table below, these additional benefits would increase total benefits to nearly 27 billion CHF, raising the net present value to [6.8 billion CHF](#) and the [benefit-cost ratio to 1.34](#).

Both scenarios may be still subject to slight adjustments and fine tuning until the end of the assignment (August 2025) but are considered solid enough for further analysis. For each category of costs and benefits, the methods, assumptions, data, and sources underpinning the CBA are thoroughly detailed in the following sections. As a next step, final estimates will be produced, and [a scenario analysis and Monte Carlo simulation will be performed](#) to estimate the probability distribution of the quantified costs and benefits and to identify the factors that most critically influence these outcomes.

¹ The assignment was awarded to CSIL in August 2024 and officially launched on September 23, 2024, in Milan. It is expected to be completed by August 2025.

Table 1: Summary results: costs and benefits of FCC-ee – Baseline Scenario

	SHARE OF THE TOTAL	TOTAL DISCOUNTED (MILLION CHF)	TOTAL NON DISCOUNTED (MILLION CHF)
TOTAL COSTS	100%	20 020	38 308
CAPEX	50.8%	10 171	16 215
OPEX	47.1%	9 423	21 212
OPEX PERSONNEL		7 544	16 802
OTHER OPERATIONAL COSTS		1 879	4 410
ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS	1.7%	354	653
GHG EMISSIONS*		342	634
RADIOACTIVE EMISSIONS		1	1.3
NOISE EMISSIONS		0.02	0.02
PRODUCTIVITY AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICE LOSS		4	8
TRAFFIC AIR POLLUTION		1	1
TRAFFIC GHG EXTERNALITIES		7	10
DISMANTLING COSTS**	0.4%	72	229
TOTAL BENEFITS	100%	23 974	56 966
THE VALUE OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION	11.7%	2 813	6 507
TRAINING BENEFITS	20.8%	4 986	20 687
INDUSTRIAL SPILLOVERS	40%	9 569	17 577
IT INNOVATIONS	18.2%	4 375	7 428
CULTURAL BENEFITS	9.3%	2 231	4 767
... FOR ONSITE VISITORS		2 129	4 538
... FOR ONLINE VISITORS		102	229
NET PRESENT VALUE		3 954	
BENEFIT / COST RATIO		1.20	

Source: Authors. **Note:** Discounted values at 0.028 Social Discount Rate. The estimates presented in this table are subject to revision * It covers the construction and operation phase. Nevertheless, it does not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator itself. ** These are considered a proxy of the decommissioning costs that would occur in a scenario without FCC-hh in order to ensure the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure.

Table 2: Summary results: costs and benefits of FCC-ee – Extended Scenario

	SHARE OF THE TOTAL	TOTAL DISCOUNTED (MILLION CHF)	TOTAL NON DISCOUNTED (MILLION CHF)
TOTAL COSTS	100%	20 020	38 308
CAPEX	50.8%	10 171	16 215
OPEX	47.1%	9 423	21 212
OPEX PERSONNEL		7 544	16 802
OTHER OPERATIONAL COSTS		1 879	4 410
ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS	1.7%	345	653
GHG EMISSIONS*		342	634
RADIOACTIVE EMISSIONS		1	1.3
NOISE EMISSIONS		0.02	0.02
PRODUCTIVITY AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICE LOSS		4	8
TRAFFIC AIR POLLUTION		1	1
TRAFFIC GHG EXTERNALITIES		7	10
DISMANTLING COSTS**	0.4%	72	229
TOTAL BENEFITS	100%	26 793	65 617
THE VALUE OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION	10.5%	2 813	6 507
TRAINING BENEFITS	18.6%	4 986	20 687
INDUSTRIAL SPILLOVERS	35.7%	9 569	17 577
IT INNOVATIONS	16.3%	4 375	7 428
CULTURAL BENEFITS	8.3%	2 231	4 767
... FOR ONSITE VISITORS		2 129	4 538
... FOR ONLINE VISITORS		102	229
ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS	0.7%	191	397
PROVISION OF EXCESS CAPACITY CLEAN ELECTRICITY TO SOCIETY		117	227
SAVINGS OF GHG EMISSIONS DUE TO HEAT RECOVERY		74	170
ECOSYSTEM BENEFITS		0.2	0.4
LOCAL IMPACTS	0.6%	148	343
REUSE OF WASTE HEAT		132	313
VALUE OF EMERGENCY SERVICES		16	30
RESIDUAL VALUE	9.3%	2 480	7 911
NET PRESENT VALUE		6 773	
BENEFIT / COST RATIO		1.34	

Source: Authors. **Note:** Discounted values at 0.028 Social Discount Rate. The estimates presented in this table are subject to revision. This scenario is based on the hypothesis that the FCC-hh will be built. * It covers the construction and operation phase. Nevertheless, it does not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator itself. **These are the costs necessary for preparing the infrastructure for the potential future FCC-hh accelerator. It does not include the cost of elimination of radioactive waste, which is expected to be estimated once the design has been completed

These figures cannot be directly compared to the results of previous socio-economic impact assessments [\[3 and 8\]](#), particularly because the latter did not integrate certain costs and benefits related to the experiments, such as collaborations' personnel and their 'first wave' publications. It is important to note that additional potential costs and benefits are excluded from the FCC-ee CBA because of fundamental uncertainties (as briefly summarised in the box below). Overall, such additional items still might have a potentially positive net impact that cannot be quantified at this stage. Hence, they must be excluded by the estimation of the net present value and benefit-cost ratio.

Box 1 Additional costs and benefits not included in the quantitative analysis

Decommissioning: Given the uncertainty surrounding the implementation of the FCC-hh, it is currently not possible to accurately estimate the decommissioning costs that CERN may incur for the FCC-ee. In a "without FCC-hh" scenario, decommissioning costs would likely be higher compared to the scenario where FCC-hh is implemented. Therefore, only some dismantling costs are included in the baseline scenario, that would be incurred in any case after the end of the scientific life of the FCC-ee.

Residual value: For economic infrastructures, such as railways, the residual value is typically defined as the market value of assets beyond the project time horizon. In the case of the FCC-ee, there is no market value, but may be a potential economic residual value after the end of operations, especially if the FCC-hh is implemented. If this occurs, the residual value of the FCC-ee—is estimated to be about 2.4 billion CHF (discounted value), as showed in Table 2 above and in Section 2.3. No residual value from the LEP was included in the cost-benefit analysis of the LHC and HL-LHC [\[see 3 and 8\]](#) as it was considered a sunk cost

IT Spin-offs, breakthrough innovation and update of digital platforms: The FCC-ee can help radical digital innovation in certain areas. Examples are quantum sensing for detectors and the integration of quantum and classic data. Artificial intelligence may assist the design of experiments in terms of data-generating processes, data taking, pattern identification and statistical inference. It is likely that some researchers and engineers involved in the FCC would start spin-off companies. However, given the rapid evolution of the technology industry, at this stage making even tentative forecasts, determining survival rates, and valuing these potential innovations is premature. A tentative valuation of simulation software is retained (Table 1, IT innovations) based on previous benchmarking with GEANT4 and others. Other digital innovations, such as the development of new digital repositories (e.g. building on the experience of Zenodo) and conference management tools (e.g. improvement of Indico), are less relevant to the FCC program considering the market and technological evolution within the business sector and would raise an attribution concern, if CERN and other entities would support updating them in future, as they currently do. For this reason, they have not been included, although significant benefits can be associated with such platforms [\[1\]](#).

Public good value: Previous CBAs of the LHC [\[3\]](#) and HL-LHC [\[8\]](#) included a benefit in terms of citizens' support for a future collider. [\[1\]](#) presents the results of a survey conducted with approximately 10,000 citizens across nine countries. In CERN member states, the median value of citizens' willingness to pay a tax increase is (typically some CHF per year), confirming the public good value of CERN investments. However, the survey does not specifically mention the FCC, but more generally future investment at CERN, while the Public Good Value included in [\[3 and 8\]](#) was more directly related to the LHC.

Costs and benefits on the local community: Capital investment costs considered in the analysis include more than 190 million CHF of infrastructure investment that not only are necessary for the project implementation but also have the potential to bring additional significant local economic benefits to the local communities. These benefits are related, for example, to the construction of a freight train access, the construction and extension of sewage and water supply networks, a cycling path and many others.

CERN is currently discussing with the local municipalities the interest and the possible arrangements for the full exploitation of such potential benefits beyond what is strictly needed for the FCC-ee. The team is currently considering whether and to what extent these benefits can be quantified and included in the analysis. In case the local community is interested in leveraging all of them, they would generate a minimum of 190 million CHF of avoided public expenditures. A more accurate assessment of social benefits, however, would require an estimation of the current and future demand for the expected local services that are currently not available, including the identification of a proper counterfactual scenario for each of them. The team will consider the inclusion of the avoided costs in the optimistic scenario and when running the Montecarlo analysis.

1. ASSUMPTIONS

1.1. Project identification

For several decades, the particle physics community has been discussing and evaluating various scenarios for the post-High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) era. These scenarios (e.g. LEP3, etc.) are designed to further investigate the Higgs mechanism and advance knowledge in fundamental physics. They differ significantly in terms of technical characteristics, such as research objectives, performance, accelerator type and size, number of experiments, location, and the reuse of existing infrastructure like pre-existing particle accelerators.

Choosing one scenario inherently involves forgoing the others. Therefore, the socio-economic impact analysis - presented in this document - considers the impacts expected to be generated by the FCC-ee only. The FCC-hh project, the second phase of the FCC integrated programme, which extends the scientific research programme until the end of the 21st century, is not considered in the baseline analysis, while in an extended version a residual value is attributed to the FCC-ee if the FCC-hh will be implemented. It is however not possible to make credible socio-economic estimates with a meaningful level of microeconomic detail and degree of confidence on such timescales.

Specifically, [the analysis considers the current design of the FCC-ee project with four major experiments](#). To present the net direct and incremental impacts of the project, this analysis will include a comparison of the estimated impacts of the FCC-ee with a “without-the-project scenario” (counterfactual scenario), as discussed in Section 1.3.

1.2. Project schedule and time horizon

According to the latest data provided by CERN (as of 30 September 2024, at this [link](#)), pre-investment feasibility studies started in 2021 and will last until 2028. The first investment costs are planned for 2029. The design and construction phases of the technical infrastructure, injector, collider, and experiments will run in parallel, each with its specific timeline (see the Table below for details).

Table 3: Detailed timeline

	DESIGN PHASE	CONSTRUCTION PHASE
Civil Engineering and technical Infrastructure	January 2027 - December 2032	January 2033 - June 2042 (technical infrastructure installed)
Injector	January 2028 - December 2031	from January 2032 to December 2040, with hardware (HW) commissioning completed by December 2041 and beam commissioning (start of experimental physics with injector) by January 2042
Collider	January 2032 - December 2038	Procurement, implementation, and installation will take place between January 2039 and December 2044
Experiments	January 2034 - December 2038, after a collaboration-building period from 2029 to 2031	Construction from January 2039 to June 2042, with installation conducted from June 2042 to December 2044

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of September 30, 2024)

For the collider and experiments, hardware commissioning is expected to be completed by December 2045. Commissioning will then take place in 2046 and 2047, with initial particle collisions occurring in 2048. The final year of operation is 2062, with the following two years expected for further data analysis.

Figure 1 below illustrates the updated FCC-ee timeline from the infrastructure design to the conclusion of the operational phase. The time horizon for the socio-economic impact analysis has been updated accordingly. It spans 41 years, from 2024 (first year of analysis) to 2064 (final year of data analysis). Past costs – related to pre-investment feasibility studies and incurred before 2024 – have been capitalised (using the GDP deflator) and included in the first year of analysis.

Figure 1 FCC-ee schedule used for the socio-economic impact analysis

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of September 30, 2024)

1.3. Counterfactual scenario

As suggested by international guidelines, the socio-economic impact analysis assesses the incremental benefits of the FCC-ee. This means that both the costs and benefits of the project are expressed incrementally in comparison to a scenario where the project is not implemented. This scenario is called the “counterfactual scenario” [6, 7].

In the framework of [1], discussions with members of the particle physics, particle accelerator, and high-energy physics communities, as well as external scientists and economists, were conducted to define this counterfactual scenario. These discussions identified the "Business-as-usual" (BAU) continuation at CERN as the counterfactual scenario for the FCC-ee (even if other accelerator concepts and scientific programs are a matter of ongoing discussion in the physics community). This scenario is assumed in the socio-economic impact analysis presented in this document. It assumes that the HL-LHC will continue operations until its expected end of life - estimated around 2040 [8] - with no new particle collider constructed afterwards. The possibility to continue with minor capital investments to the existing infrastructure to further prolong HL-LHC lifetime has been considered not credible since the science opportunities through extended operation would be negligible, but the maintenance and operation costs would be significant, thus leading to an unsustainable scenario. The counterfactual scenario may change if feasible alternatives to FCC-ee would be considered within the global scientific community.

In the estimation of all benefits for the FCC-ee project, the Team paid attention to consider only those that would be generated by the FCC-ee project, but that are not already directly attributed to the HL-LHC. For instance, the cost-benefit analysis of the HL-LHC [8] identified some benefits that would materialise after the project's end of life until 2080 (for instance, cultural and educational benefits). These benefits were not attributed to the FCC-ee project, even if they occurred during the same period.

No costs for the dismantling and disposal of the LHC are included in the FCC-ee project scenario. The LHC is assumed to mostly remain in place even if no longer operational. Some additional costs will be necessary to make the machine and the tunnel suitable for the next-generation FCC-hh project, but they remain out of the scope of this analysis. The no longer used particle accelerator and some of the experiments are assumed to serve as additional science tourist attractions based on the strong and persistent interest of CERN visitors to actually see the tunnel, the caverns, the particle accelerators and the detectors. Decommissioning would take place in the scenario without FCC-hh. It entails the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure. Since there is currently no cost estimation for this activity, in the baseline scenario – see Table 1 (Executive Summary) - it is assumed that these costs are at least equal to the dismantling costs estimated by CERN for the FCC-hh scenario (see Section 2.2 for details). Dismantling costs of FCC-ee are instead considered in the extended scenario (Table 2, Executive Summary) which rely on the assumption that FCC-hh is built. These costs will be needed to prepare the tunnel for the hosting the future FCC-hh accelerator.

1.4. Unit of measure for valuation

For this analysis, costs and benefits are reported in Swiss Francs (CHF). They are all expressed in real (constant) and non-inflation and purchasing power-adjusted terms, in line with European Commission guidelines [6, 7].

All costs and benefits are expressed in 2024 prices, and an average exchange rate over the year 2024 between CHF and all other currencies used in the analysis has been applied when currency conversion was needed (see the Tables with exchange rates used in [Annex 8.1](#)).

Monetary values do not correspond to financial cash flows but to the social welfare metrics usual in CBA that apply to any change in agents' utility.

1.5. Social Discount Rate

Costs and benefits occur at different points in time and are spread over different and long periods. Therefore, a way must be found to express them consistently and comparably at the time at one specific point in time. The Social Discount Rate (SDR) is a parameter used in the economic analysis of investment projects when inter-temporal investment decisions² have to be taken (see [Annex 7.2](#) for more details). Based on recent estimates carried out by CSIL for a major European institution, the social discount rate has been calculated based on the social rate of time preference (SRTP), which considers the social preferences and welfare of both current and future generations. Specifically, the following formula has been applied.

$$SDR = SRTP = p + \varepsilon * g$$

The Table below summarises the source of data used for each variable entering this formula. More details on the values used for calculation are presented in [Annex 8.2](#).

Table 4: Input for SDR calculation

	VARIABLE	SOURCES
p the pure time preference	It is proxied with the annual mortality rate of the population, assuming that consumption is anticipated when the risk of death or human race extinction increases	Eurostat value for 2022-2041 or the World Bank value for 2021-2040 as alternative
g the expected per-capita growth rate of consumption	It is proxied by the real growth rate of the per-capita GDP under the assumption that the GDP properly reflects the dynamics of consumption over time	Forecasts by the OECD - covering the period 2022-2041 when available, the past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the World Bank as alternative
ε the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption	It is proxied by using social preferences revealed by taxation	OECD Taxation Database for 2022, or when not available, the value estimated through value transfer (average between the regression and ML estimate considering data for 2000-2019)

Source: Authors

By applying the formula above, the team estimated the SDR in each country that contributes to the CERN budget today, including CERN Members States and Associated Countries. Then, it estimated the average of the SDR in each country, weighted by the respective contribution to the CERN budget.³

The resulting **SDR value determined by this calculation is 2.8%**. It was used to calculate the discounted value of costs and benefits preliminary presented in this document.

² When decision is taken today about using resources that are not available now, but will be in a future time.

³ Latest information gathered by 2023 CERN budget <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2888205/files/English.pdf>

2. COSTS (CAPEX + OPEX)

2.1. CAPEX

According to the latest data provided by CERN (as of 30 September 2024 at this [link](#)), the current estimate of the total investment costs, including radiofrequency for ttbar operation⁴ and total costs of four experiments, ranges between 15.3 billion CHF and 19.3 billion CHF. This represents an adjustment of approximately 3.7 billion CHF compared to [1], which was based on total investment costs of 12 billion CHF with two experiments.

The Table below details the different investment cost items, their foreseen years of occurrence and the total value expressed as an average expected cost, a more pessimistic and more optimistic estimate.

Table 5: Investment costs: structure and assumptions (undiscounted)

System	Domain	Start year of investment	Years of investment	Year of completion	Min [CHF] (95%)	Mid point [CHF] (100%)	Max [CHF] (120%)
Pre-investment and pre-construction studies	Studies	2021	11	2032	200,000,000	200,000,000	200,000,000
Collider magnets	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	869,250,000	915,000,000	1,098,000,000
Collider radiofrequency	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	551,000,000	580,000,000	696,000,000
Collider vacuum chambers	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	874,950,000	921,000,000	1,105,200,000
Power converters	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	665,950,000	701,000,000	841,200,000
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	2054	3	2057	4,750,000	5,000,000	6,000,000
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	218,500,000	230,000,000	276,000,000
Beam transfer elements	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	61,750,000	65,000,000	78,000,000
Beam intercepting devices	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	111,150,000	117,000,000	140,400,000
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	2054	3	2057	30,400,000	32,000,000	38,400,000
Beam instrumentation and diagnostics	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	196,650,000	207,000,000	248,400,000
Protection and interlock systems	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	57,950,000	61,000,000	73,200,000
Controls	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	31,350,000	33,000,000	39,600,000
Machine-Detector Interface	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	26,600,000	28,000,000	33,600,000
Machine-Detector	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	26,600,000	28,000,000	33,600,000

⁴ Radiofrequency for tt operation refers to the use of electromagnetic waves to accelerate and control protons in a particle accelerator. The RF system provides energy to the protons, keeping them in stable bunches and increasing their speed for high-energy collisions, which are necessary to produce top-antitop (tt) quark pairs in experiments like those at the Large Hadron Collider.

Interface, 2
additional
interaction points

Polarisation and energy calibration	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	19,950,000	21,000,000	25,200,000
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	2049	8	2057	1,082,050,000	1,139,000,000	1,366,800,000
Linear accelerator	Injector	2034	6	2040	234,650,000	247,000,000	296,400,000
Positron production	Injector	2034	6	2040	32,300,000	34,000,000	40,800,000
Damping ring and beam lines	Injector	2034	6	2040	68,400,000	72,000,000	86,400,000
Technical infrastructures	Injector	2032	4	2036	76,000,000	80,000,000	96,000,000
Transfer lines	Injector	2041	2	2043	144,400,000	152,000,000	182,400,000
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	2036	8	2044	196,650,000	207,000,000	248,400,000
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	2036	8	2044	2,850,000	3,000,000	3,600,000
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	617,500,000	650,000,000	780,000,000
Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	5,700,000	6,000,000	7,200,000
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	785,650,000	827,000,000	992,400,000
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	2035	5	2040	167,200,000	176,000,000	211,200,000
Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	2035	5	2040	10,450,000	11,000,000	13,200,000
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	80,750,000	85,000,000	102,000,000
Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	2034	8	2042	354,350,000	373,000,000	447,600,000
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	2038	4	2042	190,000,000	200,000,000	240,000,000
Subsurface civil engineering	CE	2033	8	2041	4,094,500,000	4,310,000,000	5,172,000,000
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	CE	2033	3	2036	0	0	0
Surface structures	CE	2040	5	2045	478,800,000	504,000,000	604,800,000

Excavated materials management *	CE	2033	8	2041	618,000,000	770,000,000	854,000,000
CE planning, management, architecture, landscaping	CE	2031	14	2045	668,800,000	704,000,000	844,800,000
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	2030	10	2040	28,500,000	30,000,000	36,000,000
20 kV connections	Territorial development	2028	5	2033	28,500,000	30,000,000	36,000,000
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	2039	10	2049	33,250,000	35,000,000	42,000,000
Access related costs	Territorial development	2028	5	2033	49,400,000	52,000,000	62,400,000
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	2037	5	2042	3,800,000	4,000,000	4,800,000
Administrative processes	Territorial development	2027	6	2033	38,000,000	40,000,000	48,000,000
Experiment 1	Experiment	2039	7	2046	346,750,000	365,000,000	438,000,000
Experiment 2	Experiment	2039	7	2046	346,750,000	365,000,000	438,000,000
Experiment 3	Experiment	2039	7	2046	285,000,000	300,000,000	360,000,000
Experiment 4	Experiment	2039	7	2046	285,000,000	300,000,000	360,000,000
TOTAL					15,300,750,000	16,215,000,000	19,348,000,000

Source: CERN communication on 30 September 2024 stating that these have been provided by a cost review panel, which ensures they are valid for approximately five years. It is based on various construction, materials, and equipment price trends observed over the past 15 years. **Note:** *New estimates for this item were provided by CERN on January 16th, 2025

Box 2 Excavated materials management

The construction of a new underground infrastructure to host the FCC machines is expected to generate about 8.2 million cubic meters (m³) of excavated material, with a distribution of about 95% molasse, 2% calcareous deposits (limestone) and 3% quaternary post-glacial and interglacial deposits.

According to the MATEX Cost Estimate Review (*FCC-2411231450-LUL-MATEX_Cost_Estimate_Review-V000.3 approved by CERN on 09/01/2025*), three scenarios have been identified for the disposal or reuse of excavated materials: A, B and C. These scenarios closely resemble the scenarios 1, 2 and 3 adopted by [1]. In particular:

- For scenario A, all the material (polluted and non-polluted) is transported by truck to disposal facilities and quarries without any treatment on-site or local valorisation. The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). In France, polluted materials are sent to ISDND (100km), and non-polluted materials to ISDI in priority and then quarries (35 km). This scenario is expected to cost around 698 MCHF, undiscounted⁵.
- For scenario B, French non-polluted material is sent to quarries at the proximity of the shaft (35 km away). French polluted material is treated on site. After de-pollution on-site, the material is sent by trucks to quarries for backfilling (no local reuse) at a distance of 65km. The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). This scenario is expected to cost around 684 MCHF, undiscounted⁶.
- For scenario C, all polluted and non-polluted material is treated on-site. Specifically, French material from experiment sites (PA, PD, PG, PJ) is reused in the vicinity of the shafts; non-polluted material from these sites is also used for landscaping. Material from technical sites (PF, PH, PL) is sent towards quarries in the proximity of the shaft for landfilling purposes (25km away). The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). This scenario is expected to cost around 448 MCHF, undiscounted⁷.

During a meeting with CERN staff (held on January 24th, 2025), it was clarified that scenario A would not comply with the current French legislation, which mandates that a certain percentage of excavated material is reused. As a result, it was decided to exclude scenario A from the cost estimation and to use the weighted average of the overall costs for material transport, disposal and the construction of the treatment facilities in scenarios B and C as the baseline (i.e. 600 MCHF). On top of the costs related to the transportation and the construction of the treatment facilities, an additional 170 MCHF of energy consumption, maintenance costs, and manpower for the sorting facilities need to be added to obtain the final estimate. The best-case and worst-case scenarios correspond to scenarios B and C, respectively. Considering the additional 170 MCHF of manpower, energy, and maintenance costs needed to sort materials, the best-case and the worst-case scenarios become 618,000,000 and 854,000,000, respectively.

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of January 9, 16 and 24th, 2025)

The figure below depicts the time profile of FCC-ee total investment costs, which was agreed with CERN (as of 14th November 2024 and stored at this [link](#)). It was developed by distributing the total expected investment costs over time based on when investments for each subsystem are expected. Specifically, the distribution accounts for a gradual ramp-up of expenses, following a realistic scheduling scheme, and incorporates a two-year payment delay relative to the expected completion of investments for each item (excluding pre-investment studies). This delay is typical when payments are tied to the acceptance of deliverables.

It is worth pointing out that this curve represents the annual investment costs. The actual cash inflow to CERN as well as the actual outflow to contractors, may differ—and likely will. However, this is not intended to be a financial planning study.

Figure 2 Total profile of investment costs (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of 30 September 2024 and 14th November 2024)

As a next step, the team will also assess potential scenarios involving delays in the construction phase and the consequent postponement of the operational phase. Drawing on existing literature, both worst-case and best-case scenarios may be considered, with cost variations exceeding those assumed in the table above.

2.2. Dismantling costs

The dismantling costs of FCC-ee will be incurred if FCC-hh is built (Extended Scenario, Table 2 in the Executive Summary), as they are necessary to prepare its installation. According to CERN data (as of February 3, 2025), these costs are estimated at approximately 216.2 MCHF (2023 prices). These costs are expected to incur in 2065 and 2066, following two final years of data analysis. CERN estimated these figures in November 2024 based on the dismantling costs of LEP. When adjusted to 2024 prices and evenly distributed across the two years, the total undiscounted cost amounts to 227.9 MCHF, with a discounted cost of 72.4 MCHF. In the Baseline Scenario (Table 1, Executive Summary) - where it is assumed that FCC-hh will not be built - the dismantling costs for FCC-ee are considered a conservative estimate for decommissioning costs (for which no estimation is available to date). These costs would occur to ensure the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure.

Table 6: Total dismantling costs – (CHF, 2024)

	Discounted	Not discounted
Dismantling Costs	72,447,506	227,874,800

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of February 3rd, 2025)

2.3. Residual value

For economic infrastructures such as railways, the residual value is typically defined as the market value of assets beyond the project's time horizon. In the case of the FCC-ee, certain assets may retain value as they can be repurposed for the subsequent FCC-hh project.

Based on CERN data (as of February 3, 2025), the calculation follows a simplified and conservative approach in four steps:

1. **Asset Identification:** CERN identified the assets expected to retain residual value at the end of the FCC-ee phase. These include RF systems for Z and ttbar operation modes, the electricity infrastructure, ventilation and cooling systems, and all subsurface and surface civil structures. While additional systems may hold residual value, they have been excluded for prudence.
2. **Residual Share Estimation:** CERN determined the share of the initial investment cost that will retain value for the FCC-hh, considering ongoing maintenance and repairs during the FCC-ee's operational lifetime (costs already accounted for in operating expenses, see Section 3.2).
3. **Residual Value Calculation:** the estimated residual shares were applied to the initial investment costs to determine the retained value for each asset.
4. **Discounting:** the Social Discount Rate was applied to compute the final discounted residual asset value.

The total residual value of assets built during the FCC-ee phase is estimated in 2066 at approximately 7.9 billion MCHF (undiscounted), which corresponds to 55% of the total FCC-ee investment costs. The discounted value is 2.5 billion MCHF. This residual value has been incorporated into the extended scenario.

Table 7: Items with residual value beyond 2064 (CHF)

TIME HORIZON	DOMAIN	SHARE OF RESIDUAL VALUE	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL NOT DISCOUNTED
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	20%	313,537	1,000,000
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	20%	14,422,715	46,000,000
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	20%	2,006,639	6,400,000
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	80%	285,695,168	911,200,000
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	50%	32,451,108	103,500,000
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	50%	470,306	1,500,000
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	50%	101,899,616	325,000,000
Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	50%	940,612	3,000,000
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	85%	220,401,030	702,950,000
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	100%	55,182,561	176,000,000

Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	100%	3,448,910	11,000,000
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	100%	26,650,669	85,000,000
Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	100%	116,949,405	373,000,000
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	100%	62,707,456	200,000,000
Subsurface civil engineering	CE	100%	1,351,345,670	4,310,000,000
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	CE	100%	0	0
Surface structures	CE	100%	158,022,788	504,000,000
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	100%	9,406,118	30,000,000
20 kV connections	Territorial development	100%	9,406,118	30,000,000
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	100%	10,973,805	35,000,000
Access related costs	Territorial development	100%	16,303,938	52,000,000
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	100%	1,254,149	4,000,000
Total			2,480,252,318	7,910,550,000

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of February 3rd, 2025)

2.4. OPEX

Operation costs include all disbursements (both in-kind and outflows) needed to operate, maintain, and repair the FCC-ee research infrastructure during the entire project time horizon. In what follows, we describe in detail the costs considered for the FCC-ee by distinguishing between personnel and other costs.

2.4.1. Personnel

According to data provided by CERN (as of 14 October 2024, at this [link](#)), the current FCC-ee design involves approximately 258,000 person-years over its entire lifecycle (2024–2064), encompassing design, construction, operation, and data analysis, with a peak of more than 15,428 individuals in 2060. This diverse group consists of scientists, engineers, technicians, administrative staff, doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, undergraduate and Master’s students, and apprentices. Of the total personnel, around 11% are expected to work on particle accelerators and technical infrastructures, while the remaining 89% will focus on detectors and experimental physics.

Table 8: Number of person-years, summary results

2024-2064	ACCELERATOR & INFRASTRUCTURE	EXPERIMENTS (1+2+3+4)	TOTAL
<i>Scientists</i>	3,320	33,783	37,103
<i>Post docs</i>	6,690	61,453	68,143
<i>Engineers</i>	2,420	47,735	50,155
<i>Technicians</i>	7,489	16,270	23,759
<i>Administration</i>	1,303	2,124	3,427
<i>Doctoral students</i>	3,735	44,142	47,877
<i>Other students</i>	1,850	24,406	26,256
<i>Apprentices</i>	788	600	1,388
Total	27,594	230,513	258,107
SHARE	11%	89%	100%

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

As shown in the Figure below, these personnel will be involved in the FCC-ee programme since 2028 and will follow a ramp-up phase, increasing from a minimum of 495 persons in 2028 to a maximum of 15,428 in 2060 during the operational phase.

Figure 3 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee programme by phase

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Figure 4 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee programme by categories

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Figure 5 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee accelerator and infrastructure by categories

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Figure 6 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee experiments by categories

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Figure 7 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee by experiments

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Out of the total personnel-year number (258,107), approximately 21% will be present on-site and directly managed by CERN, while the remaining 79% will be affiliated with various other external institutions located across high-income, middle-income, and low-income countries. These institutions actively contribute to CERN's experiments by providing expertise, resources, and personnel as part of international collaborative efforts. Unlike the previous cost-benefit analyses (CBA) for the LHC and HL-LHC [see references 3, 8], the analysis presented in this document - in line with [1] - also includes the costs associated with personnel affiliated and managed by other external institutions. The table below summarizes the number of personnel-years involved in the FCC-ee program, distinguishing between categories and identifying those managed by CERN and those affiliated with other institutions.

Table 9: Number of personnel-years managed by CERN and by other institutions, summary results

2024-2064	ACCELERATOR & INFRASTRUCTURE		EXPERIMENTS (1+2+3+4)		TOTAL		TOTAL FCC-EE PROGRAMME
	MANAGED BY CERN	MANAGED BY OTHER INSTITUTIONS	MANAGED BY CERN	MANAGED BY OTHER INSTITUTIONS	MANAGED BY CERN	MANAGED BY OTHER INSTITUTIONS	
Scientists	2,490	830	2,703	31,080	5,192	31,910	37,103
Post docs	5,084	1,606	4,916	56,537	10,001	58,143	68,143
Engineers	1,815	605	3,819	43,916	5,634	44,521	50,155
Technicians	5,616	1,872	16,270	-	21,886	1,872	23,759
Administration	977	326	170	1,954	1,147	2,280	3,427
Doctoral students	2,839	896	3,531	40,611	6,370	41,507	47,877
Other students	1,850	-	1,952	22,454	3,802	22,454	26,256
Apprentices	788	-	300	300	1,088	300	1,388
Total	21,460	6,135	33,661	196,852	55,121	202,986	258,107
SHARE					21%	79%	100%

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

Figure 8 Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee managed by CERN versus other institutions

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14, 2024)

To estimate personnel costs, a clear distinction was made between personnel directly managed by CERN and those managed by external institutions. This approach is based on the assumption that the costs of personnel from external institutions should reflect the diverse economic contexts of their countries of

origin⁸. Two different average annual gross salaries⁹ were applied to account for this difference, as shown in the Table below. Specifically, for personnel managed by CERN – and in particular, for the categories Scientists, Engineer, Technician, and Administration - the team relied on the salaries estimated by Deloitte¹⁰ (shared by CERN as of October 14, 2024, accessible at this [link](#)). As for the other categories of personnel – such as Doctoral students, Postdocs, Undergraduate students (that we assume includes Master’s students), and Apprentices – the Team relied on the information provided by CERN (on the basis of current salary conditions (as of 22 October 2024 and 14 January 2025 at this [link](#)). As for the salaries of personnel managed by other institutions, the Team consulted different sources [[9, Eurostat, OECD, Glassdoor](#)], which indicated that these salaries are, on average, 20% lower than those applied to personnel managed by CERN.

⁸ For instance, the current composition of personnel from external institutions involved in LHC experiments is as follows: 81% are from high-income countries, 15% from upper-middle-income countries, and 4% from lower-middle-income countries. Among these, the United States contributes the largest share, accounting for 20% of the total personnel, followed by Italy, which represents nearly 15%. Source: <https://greybook.cern.ch/> Accessed on 28.11.2024.

⁹ It is made of net salary, employee social contributions, Employer contributions (charge patronale). Fixed overhead for indirect labour costs of management and administration are excluded, , as usual in CBA.

¹⁰ Provision of corporate development organisational, financial, legal and tax consultancy services at CERN”, Deloitte, 6 Place de la Pyramide, 92800 Puteaux, France, CERN Purchase Requisition 10697471, June 2024

Table 10: Total assumed labour costs per person by job category in 2024 CHF values

	CERN, CHF	SOURCE	OTHER INSTITUTIONS, CHF
Scientist	211,915	Deloitte's study estimated an average gross annual salary of €136,332. However, following discussions with CERN (on January 14th and 20th, 2025), it was concluded that this figure was too low to accurately reflect the salaries of personnel managed by CERN. Instead, it was decided to use CERN's current salary scale – EUR 222,460 – to ensure a more realistic and precise estimation of personnel costs.	169,532
Post-doctoral student	84,318	Based on discussions with CERN on January 14th and 20th, 2025, the team decided to use the salary values outlined in the STATUT ET RÈGLEMENT DU PERSONNEL (updated on January 1, 2025), specifically the table on page 72. This estimation is derived from the monthly salary for a Fellow, set at 4,779 CHF, combined with an average monthly supplement ranging between 750 CHF and 3,745 CHF.	67,454
Engineer	129,870	Deloitte study's estimation	103,896
Technician	78,681	Deloitte study's estimation	62,945
Administration	58,725	Deloitte study's estimation	46,980
Doctoral student	43,515	CERN suggested a value of 58,020 CHF on the basis of https://careers.cern/salary-conditions . During the meeting held on January 14 th , it was clarified that this value also included 25% overheads, which was excluded for this analysis.	34,812
Undergraduate students	38,835	CERN suggested a value of 51,780 CHF on the basis of https://careers.cern/salary-conditions . During the meeting held on January 14 th , it was clarified that this value also included 25% overheads, which was excluded for this analysis. We assume this includes other students, such as Master's students	31,068
Apprentices	12,885	CERN suggested this value based on the following assumptions: on average, over 4 years, the gross salary for an apprentice is 1073 CHF per month and 12 885 CHF annually. This salary is paid by CERN, and it does not include overheads (as confirmed on January 15th, 2025).	10,308

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of October 14 and 22, November 28, 2024; January 20, 2025)

In addition, and only for the scientists managed by external institutions, in order to appropriately attribute the personnel effort to FCC-ee, the team accounted for the following assumptions :

1. In line with [1], the Team consider that scientists spend about 55% of their time performing scientific research and writing articles, with the remainder allocated to administrative tasks, teaching activities, writing grant applications, outreach, etc. Other sources, such as [2], use 65%. The uncertainty will be treated at a later stage.
2. Out of the time addressed to research, the Team, as confirmed by experts' opinion, also considered that these scientists dedicate only a share of their time to FCC-ee-related activities, the remaining time being dedicated to other experiments. This share was estimated by considering the LHC-related products produced by scientists as compared to their total scientific output. This information was sourced from [2].

Since the analysis is conducted in real (constant) terms, inflation is excluded from the cost calculations. As a result, the annual labour costs were assumed to remain constant throughout the entire project duration.

The following table provides a summary of the total costs of the personnel over the period 2028-2064.

Table 11: Personnel costs, summary results

2028-2064	CHF (DISCOUNTED)	CHF (NOT DISCOUNTED)	SHARE
PERSONNEL COST FOR THE ENTIRE FCC-EE PROGRAMME (A+B) OR (C+D)	7,544,201,718	16,802,168,088	
(A) PERSONNEL COST MANAGED BY CERN	2,383,709,068	4,903,561,514	29%
(B) PERSONNEL COST MANAGED BY OTHER INSTITUTIONS	5,160,492,650	11,898,606,574	71%
(C) PERSONNEL COST ACCELERATOR & INFRASTRUCTURE	1,205,071,940	2,248,083,533	13%
(D) PERSONNEL COST EXPERIMENTS (1+2+3+4)	6,339,129,778	14,554,084,555	87%

Source: Authors

The figure below shows the estimated trend of personnel costs.

Figure 9 Labour costs covered by CERN and by the worldwide collaborations (CHF 2024, not discounted)

Source: Authors

Figure 10 Labour costs for Accelerator & Infrastructure versus Experiments (CHF 2024, not discounted)

Source: Authors

2.4.2. Other operational costs

In addition to personnel, the following operational costs are included in the analysis on the basis of data and information shared by CERN (on 18 December 2024, at this [link](#)):

- **Maintenance and repair:** they include the equipment and materials costs necessary for keeping the buildings and the facilities in good condition including expenditures to fix broken parts and replacement of spare parts. In addition to ordinary maintenance costs, they include some costs that will occur during the operation phase for the replacement and upgrade of some fixed assets. For instance, they include the repair and maintenance of tunnels and buildings, maintenance and repair of cryogenic systems, maintenance and repair of magnet systems, and Maintenance and repair of 4 experiments (covered mainly by other institutions). These costs have been estimated by CERN based on the latest data available from CERN financial statement 2023.
- **Goods and services:** they refer to any raw or (semi)processed materials and components necessary for the project operation, including their transport costs from the source of supply to the facility. For the FCC-ee they refer to consumables related to electronics and electrical engineering, IT radiation monitoring and protection equipment, radiofrequency equipment, office materials and other materials that are needed for day-to-day operation. Insurance costs and other industrial service contracts are included. All these costs are estimated by considering the historical CERN operational expenditure for the years 2019-2023 and the quantity of goods and services expected to be consumed by the project.
- **Communication, meetings, and events:** it includes promotional campaigns, the organisation of scientific conferences and workshops and other outreach expenditures associated with the FCC-ee project
- **Cryogenics:** consumables used by the FCC-ee project include the liquid helium (lHe) and nitrogen (lN) used as cryogenics. They are estimated by considering the historical CERN operational expenditure for the years 2019-2020 and the quantity of cryogenics expected to be consumed by the project. According to information provided by CERN, FCC-ee is not expected to make extensive use of gases.
- **Electricity and Water:** they are estimated by considering the estimated unit prices of the goods and the quantities expected to be consumed by the project. Specifically, as for electricity, following the FCC Sustainable Energy Supply concept developed by CERN, it is assumed that renewable energy sources would supply the major share of electricity through a number of stacked Power Purchasing Agreements (PPA) of 75 to 85 EUR per MWh. Benefits arising from the use of renewable energy sources are discussed and quantified in Section 5.2.1. As for water, the quantities have been updated to reflect newer, more accurate estimates. The baseline scenario corresponds to roughly 1.28 million m³/y, namely the amount of water consumed each year in the waste heat scenario 2. The price considered is 0.85 CHF/m³.

The Table below shows the average annual operation costs by domain, excluding the personnel costs.

Table 12: ANNUAL operating costs of FCC-ee by domain excluding personnel costs (CHF 2024, not discounted).

	CHF	%	NOTES
Civil engineering and buildings	3,500,000		Based on CERN financial statements for 2023 and the assumption that the FCC buildings are all new.
Low temperature	1,300,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Magnets	606,667		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Particle detectors	10,000,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Subtotal maintenance and repair	15,406,667	7%	
Electronics and electrical engineering	11,600,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Health, safety and environment	2,267,667		Based on CERN financial statements 2023, assumed at 50% of CEPS
Information technology	12,000,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values (collaborations will cover at least part of them)
Measuring instruments	1,600,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Mechanical engineering and raw materials	15,000,000		It includes a cooling and ventilation system. It is assumed 1.5% annually of 1 billion of investment
Office supply and equipment	1,200,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Optics and photonics	450,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Other supplies	200,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Radiation equipment	15,000		Assumed that 50% of 2023 value will be accounted to FCC-ee
Radiofrequency systems (electrical, mechanical, electronics)	21,000,000		It is assumed 3% of the 700 million investment
Transport, handling and vehicles	1,200,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Vacuum and particle detection equipment/supplies	2,800,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Service contracts	42,400,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Insurance	3,000,000		2019-2023 value
Transport	500,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal goods and services	115,232,667	50%	
Communication	1,000,000		2019-2023 value
Training	1,000,000		2019-2023 value

Visits and conferences	2,910,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal communication, meetings, events	4,910,000	2%	
Gases and chemicals	110,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal cryogenics	110,000	0.0%	
Subtotal electricity	92,547,368	40%	Consumption and prices based on data provided by CERN (GHG emissions, OPEX). 22.65 TWh at 80CHF/MWh.
Subtotal water	1,453,469	1%	Based on waste heat scenarios. 24.3 mln m3 at 0.85 CHF/m3
TOTAL	229,660,170	100%	

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication on December 18th, 2024

The costs are expected to fluctuate throughout the project's operation, depending on the operational phase. As illustrated in the figure below, a slight decrease is observed in 2057. This is due to the absence of cryogenics-related costs that year, as the machine is planned to undergo an upgrade.

Based on these assumptions, other operational costs are estimated to be 4.4. billion CHF (not discounted) for the period 2046-2064.

Figure 11 Other Operational costs (not discounted)

Source: Authors

2.4.3. Total OPEX

The total operational costs are expected to be around 9.4 billion CHF (discounted value) for the period 2024-2064, with about 80% allocated for personnel costs.

Table 13: Total estimation of OPEX – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024)

	Discounted	Not discounted	Share
PERSONNEL (FROM CERN)	2,383,709,068	4,903,561,514	
PERSONNEL (FROM OTHER INSTITUTIONS)	5,160,492,650	11,898,606,574	
SUBTOTAL PERSONNEL	7,544,201,718	16,802,168,088	80%
ELECTRICITY	763,939,368	1,812,000,000	
MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR	125,966,519	292,726,667	
GOOD AND SERVICES	939,589,231	2,189,420,667	
COMMUNICATION, MEETINGS, EVENTS	40,035,376	93,290,000	
CRYOGENS	884,411	2,090,000	
WATER	8,585,942	20,683,983	
SUBTOTAL (EXCL. PERSONNEL)	1,879,000,847	4,410,211,316	20%
TOTAL	9,423,202,565	21,212,379,404	100%

Source: Authors

The figure below shows the estimated trend of the total OPEX, including both personnel and other operational expenditures.

Figure 12 Total Operation costs, not discounted

Source: Authors

As a next step, the team will assume a worst-case and best-case scenario, which considers variations of certain cost items (e.g. electricity, etc.) to determine their suitability and will revise them accordingly. Residual uncertainty will be dealt with in Montecarlo simulations.

3. ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS

3.1. GHG emissions

Introduction

The negative externality is given by the [greenhouse gas \(GHG\) emissions](#) expressed in CO2 equivalent (CO2eq) generated by the FCC-ee project during both the [construction](#) of the tunnel and surface sites as well as the [operation phase](#).

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 - Quantifying the GHG emissions

The quantities of CO2 equivalent generated during the construction of the subsurface (the tunnel) and the surface sites (comprising four experimental and four technical sites) of FCC-ee were estimated in the context of an LCA study¹¹ conducted by WSP on behalf of CERN. The quantities are summarized in the table below. It is worth noting that the study did not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator itself. The estimated total emissions were distributed over the construction period according to the workflow.

Table 14: Tons of CO2(eq) for the construction of the subsurface and the surface sites

STAGE	SUB-SURFACE	EXPERIMENTAL SITE*	TECHNICAL SITE*	TOTAL*
A1 - A3 (Products)	364.301	6.716	2.153	399.777
A4 (Transport)	68.318	242	78	69.596
A5 (Construction)	44.771	204	173	46.279
B3 (Repair)	0	0	0	0
B4 - B5 (Usage)	0	282	12	1.177
B6 (energy)	0	0	0	0
C1 - C4 (decommissioning)	0	489	1.972	9.842
Total	477.390	7.934	4.387	526.671

Note: * the values for experimental and technical sites refer to a single site in the column with a total of four technical sites, and four experimental sites were considered. **Source:** Authors based on LCA study performed by WSP

According to CERN, during operation, the FCC-ee will consume a total of 22.65 TWh of electricity, 80% of which is supplied by renewable energy sources (RES), assumed to be covered by wind power and solar PV.¹² The remaining 20% will be purchased from the grid. It is assumed that this portion will be supplied by the French electricity grid, as is currently the case for the LHC. In the best-case scenario, the percentage of electricity from RES would increase to 95%, while in the worst-case scenario, it would decrease to 60%.

¹¹ Carried out in line with the European standard Norm EN 17472, which provides requirements and guidelines for calculating and reporting GHG emissions associated with infrastructure projects

¹² The feasibility of such endeavour has been explored in two high-level exploratory studies prepared by external consultants in 2023 (Accenture, McKinsey).

Some GHG emission optimization measures are planned for both the construction and operation phases. In the construction phase, GHG emissions are primarily driven by concrete and reinforced steel production. This creates opportunities for emission reduction through the establishment of new technical requirements, careful material selection, optimization of construction processes and improvements in energy efficiency. Overall, CERN is confident in achieving a 2% reduction in emissions during construction. In the operation phase, reduced cooling needs due to waste heat re-use, improved design of certain accelerator components, and other targeted interventions are expected to reduce energy consumption by around 20%. These emissions reductions are reflected in the calculations.

To quantify the CO₂eq emissions, appropriate emission factors are applied. Different energy sources produce different quantities of GHG emissions. For the share of RES electricity, the emission factors for off-shore wind and photovoltaic production are used, while for the share of mixed-sources (grid) electricity, the emission factor for electricity consumption in France is adopted. The table below shows the respective factors and the combined weighted factor. In line with the objective of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, France plans to further reduce the carbon intensity of its electricity production by a factor of almost three by 2050¹³. In other words, the emission factor for the consumption of the French electricity grid is expected to decrease over time. Accordingly, a constant annual decrease is assumed in the baseline scenario (4%), in the best-case scenario (5%), and in the worst-case scenario (3%) until 2050.

Table 15: CO₂(eq) intensity of FCC-ee electricity consumption during the operational phase

	Share	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2024)	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2046)	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2050)
Baseline scenario				
Off-shore wind	60%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	20%	58.00	23.68	20.07
Combined factor	100%	26.00	19.10	18.41
Best-case scenario				
Off-shore wind	75%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	5%	58.00	18.76	15.28
Combined factor	100%	19.64	17.68	17.50
Worst-case scenario				
Off-shore wind	40%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	40%	58.00	29.68	26.27
Combined factor	100%	34.48	23.15	21.79

Source: ADEME Base Carbone for emission factors of off-shore wind, photovoltaic and FR consumption mix in 2024.

¹³ I. Tiseo, Carbon intensity outlook of the power sector in France from 2020 to 2050.

Table 16: Total tCO₂(eq) emissions of FCC-ee

	Baseline	Best-case scenario	Worst-case scenario
Emissions related to the construction of the subsurface and surface structures	526,671	526,671	526,671
Scope 2 emissions related to operation	418,195	396,745	495,698
TOTAL	944,866	923,416	1,022,369
TOTAL OPTIMISED	850,693	833,534	912,696

Source: Authors

Figure 13: Total GHG emissions from the project during construction and operation in the reference scenario in tCO₂eq, 2030-2064

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO₂eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal [see 7].¹⁴ One ton of CO₂eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO₂eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

The table below presents the total externality (covering both the construction and operation phases) from GHG emissions attributable to the FCC-ee project. As noted in a previous paragraph, the present

¹⁴ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see [39] in Reference section.

calculation of the total externality does not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator. In the baseline scenario, the total externality amounts to 633 million CHF (undiscounted). The discounted present value of the externality is 341 million CHF. In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value rises to 367 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it decreases to 334 million CHF.

Table 17: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024)

Scenario	Total discounted	Total undiscounted
Baseline	341,308,153	633,079,473
Worst-case scenario	366,863,543	693,661,167
Best-case scenario	334,208,664	616,349,004

Source: Authors

3.2. Ionising radiation

Introduction

The FCC-ee will generate ionising radiation during the collision of particle beams with matter. Despite the modest contribution of the FCC-ee in terms of radioactive emissions compared to the natural amount of radiation already present in the environment, the cautionary approach, recommended by various guidelines¹⁵, suggests the adoption of a linear dose-response curve with no threshold, thus including also very small increases in radiation.¹⁶

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 - Quantifying the radioactive emissions

The Man-Sievert metric was chosen to quantify the exposure of individuals to ionising radiation. Measuring ionizing radiation in Man-Sievert allows measuring the biological impact of a collective dose of radiation for a group of people. For example, a collective dose of 1 Man-Sievert corresponds to 100,000 persons who receive 10 μ Sievert per year. This metric is widely adopted by the International Atomic Energy Agency and is the method used in France to estimate the radiological component of the environmental impact of nuclear power plants.

While the annual dose limit for public exposure from artificial sources in Europe is 1 millisievert (mSv), CERN commits to keeping its contribution below 0.3 mSv per year. The radiation emissions attributable to existing particle accelerators are even lower, estimated to be less than 0.01 mSv/y, equivalent to 10 microSievert/year (μ Sv/y)¹⁷. The latter is the amount of exposure that is used for the quantification of ionizing radiation externalities. For context, the natural background level of ionizing radiation in the municipalities surrounding CERN ranges between 0.6 and 0.9 mSv/y.

¹⁵ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, ExternE – Externalities of Energy. Volume 5, Nuclear, Publications Office, 1995; INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Approaches to Cost-Benefit Analysis of New Nuclear Power Projects, IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NG-T-4.8, IAEA, Vienna (2024)

¹⁶ The following analysis calculate the externality associated to the population exposure, while the exposure of fauna and flora is not considered, as it would be negligible given the already minimal radiation levels associated to the local population.

¹⁷ See [19] in Reference section.

To estimate the negative externality associated with radioactive emissions, the population affected by ionising radiation from FCC-ee has been identified, i.e. those residing and working near the emission source. CERN staff (occupationally exposed) were not considered because the number of people (without risking double-counting) remains uncertain. Moreover, they can be legally exposed to a higher regulatory limit of 6 mSv/year, which is double the amount of radiation that is applied in practice at CERN¹⁸, and their salary generally accounts for the additional risks or inconveniences associated with the job (i.e. salary internalise, at least partially, the negative effects of radiation).

To estimate the number of persons exposed to ionizing radiation, a 300-meter radius from the 8 sites of the FCC infrastructure was drawn in every direction. This distance was chosen because, by applying the inverse square law, the intensity of the radiation decreases quadratically with the distance in meters from the access shaft. Assuming a maximum of 10 µSv at the ventilation exit, therefore, gives 0.0001 µSv at 300 meters (a negligible exposure).

For each house and apartment building found within the 300m radius, the total amount of residents was calculated using data from the *Swiss Federal Statistical Office* and the *French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies*. The number of workers was obtained by estimating the number of employees for each economic activity found within the 300m radius. We assumed that residents spend 70% of their time at home while workers spend 33% of their time at their workplace. The total amount of people affected by radiation is estimated to be 1522.

Table 18: Total number of inhabitants and workers potentially affected by radiation.

SITE	NUMBER OF INHABITANTS (70%)	NUMBER OF WORKERS (33%)	TOTAL
PA, Ferney-Voltaire	689	437	1126
PB, Presinge (CH)	15	0	15
PD, Nangy	50	79	129
PF, Éteaux	172	45	217
PG, Charvonnex/Groisy	8	2	10
PH, Marlioz	19	0	19
PJ, Dingy-en-Vuache et Vulbens	0	0	0
PL, Challex	7	0	7
Total	960	562	1522

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

Most nuclear regulatory authorities and utilities worldwide have adopted a single or a system of monetary values of ionising radiations, expressed in terms of €/man.Sv. This “reference monetary value of the man sievert” is constantly updated to reflect the state-of-the-art methodology in calculating the Value of Statistical Life. In 2020, the EDF¹⁹ updated its reference monetary value to account for the most recent recommendations from the International Commission on Radiological Protection and the French

¹⁸ According to information produced by CERN (i.e. [19]), there are no instances of workers receiving a dose higher than 1,3 mSv/year in the 2021-2022 reporting period.

¹⁹ Électricité de France S.A.

State administration. The new reference value was estimated to be 4,500 €2017/man.mSv.²⁰ This value applies to all levels of radiation exposure, contrary to the EDF's previous approach of providing increasing values for increasing levels of absorbed doses.

Results

By multiplying the above reference monetary value of the man sievert with the annual dose of radiation exposure and the number of affected persons, it is possible to obtain the ionizing radiation-related externality. For each year of operation, the FCC-ee will cause a yearly negative externality of EUR 83,241.98. By multiplying this value by the number of years of operation — from 2047 to 2062, including one year of transition—a value of EUR 1,331,872 (or CHF 1,268,714) is obtained. The discounted value instead is estimated to be EUR 578,343 (or CHF 550,930).

Table 19: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024)

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED (CHF)	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED (CHF)
Baseline	550,930	1,268,741

Source: Authors

3.3. Radioactive waste

Introduction

The synchrotron radiation emitted by the high-energy leptons will strike the localised absorbers in the vacuum chamber and will induce radioactivity. Other areas expected to become radioactive are beam scrapers, collimators, shields, beamstrahlung main beam dumps and, to some extent, the magnets. Elements that absorb a high fraction of the beam power will need to be considered as radioactive waste.

The disposal of radioactive waste is governed by the tripartite agreement on radiation protection and radiation safety between CERN and its Host States. Article 7 of this tripartite agreement, which defines the principles governing CERN's elimination of radioactive waste, allows CERN to eliminate radioactive waste in the two Host States by using the most technically and economically advantageous pathways in both countries.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the radioactive waste volume

None of the existing CERN accelerator facilities is required to be modified or dismantled ahead or for the FCC-ee construction and operation, which would lead to the production of radioactive waste. Therefore, no production of radioactive waste linked to the construction of the FCC-ee is expected.

FCC-ee will be operated in four phases (Z, W, H, and ttbar) that are separated by three longer shutdown periods to implement the required upgrades for the accelerator and the experiments. As FCC-ee will be an entirely new machine designed to run without the need to replace large quantities of equipment during its operational lifetime, the expected volumes of radioactive waste generated during the

²⁰ See [20] in Reference section.

operation of the FCC-ee, including its injector complex, should be small compared to the absolute size of the facilities.

After completion of the FCC-ee physics programme, it is expected that the FCC-ee booster and collider will be completely dismantled to prepare the infrastructure for the installation of the next accelerator, the FCC-hh. The dismantling of the FCC-ee booster, collider, and experiments will require the removal of all accelerator components and detectors, thus producing radioactive waste. However, the dismantling phase is not included in the present study, as it is considered part of the initial phase of the next project (FCC-hh).

The table below summarises the roughly estimated volumes of radioactive waste for the different classes in this preliminary study phase of the FCC-ee.

Table 20: Estimates of radioactive waste volume for FCC-ee during the operation phase and dismantling

	NEGLECTIBLE ACTIVATION (CL)	VERY LOW ACTIVATION (TFA)	LOW AND INTERMEDIATE ACTIVATION WITH SHORT HALF-LIFES (FMA-VC)	LOW AND INTERMEDIATE ACTIVATION (FA-MA)
Operating phase				
Injector complex	< 50 m ³ per year	< 5 m ³ per year	< 1 m ³ per year	-
FCC-ee accelerator	< 200 m ³ per year	< 20 m ³ per year	< 1 m ³ per year	-
FCC-ee experiments	< 50 m ³ per year < 100 m ³ per LS	< 5 m ³ per year < 10 m ³ per LS	< 1 m ³ per year < 5 m ³ per LS	-
Total (15 years, 3 LS)	< 5000 m³	< 500 m³	< 60 m³	-
Dismantling phase				
FCC-ee accelerator	< 11,000 m ³	< 8,000 m ³	< 130 m ³	< 10 m ³
FCC-ee experiments	< 2,000 m ³	< 1,000 m ³	< 10 m ³	-
Total	< 13,000 m³	< 9,000 m³	< 140 m³	< 10 m³

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication **Note:** LS stands for long shutdown.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The cost estimate for the disposal of radioactive waste from CERN's facilities is based on an inventory indicating the amount and radiotoxicity of present and future radioactive waste, i.e. waste stored at CERN and waste that will be produced by preventive and corrective maintenance or by the upgrade of CERN's facilities or experiments. Based on the information shared by CERN (as of December 17th, 2024), the estimate for the elimination cost of future radioactive waste during operation (see table below) is already included in the operation budget (i.e. OPEX). This aligns with the approach suggested, for example, by the IAEA guide [40], which foresees that all costs for the treatment and disposal of radioactive waste are typically 'internalized' as part of the operating costs of a nuclear power plant. At the same time, the elimination costs associated with dismantling are accounted for only in the Extended Scenario (see Table 2, Executive Summary), which assumes the subsequent construction of the FCC-hh.

Table 21: Estimates for the elimination costs of radioactive waste produced by FCC-ee (CHF)

TOTAL	NEGLIGIBLE ACTIVATION (CL)	VERY LOW ACTIVATION (TFA)	LOW AND INTERMEDIATE ACTIVATION WITH SHORT HALF-LIFES (FMA-VC)	LOW AND INTERMEDIATE ACTIVATION (FA-MA)
Operating phase				
2,200,000*	-	<500,000*	<1,700,000*	-
Dismantling phase				
13,500,000	-	<7,500,000	<3,500,000	<2,500,000

*15 years, 3 LS. **Source:** Authors processing of CERN communication

3.4. Noise

Introduction

FCC-ee is going to generate noise during both the construction and operation phases. The presence of noise in the vicinity of the construction sites carries a non-auditory cost on society, which is mainly related to sleep disturbance and annoyance. Other effects of noise include hypertension and loss of productivity.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the negative noise externality

Estimating the negative noise externality requires quantifying both the number of affected individuals and the intensity of the noise (noise levels) for the construction phase and for the operation phase. During construction, noise emissions primarily stem from the preparation and construction of the surface sites, the construction of the shaft, and the excavation of the underground infrastructure. During operation, the noise is mainly caused by the ventilation system for the underground structures.

To quantify the number of people exposed to noise from the FCC’s construction and operation, the number of inhabitants within 100-meter and 200-meter radii (the same distances used to measure noise levels) were estimated by counting the apartments within each area and multiplying by the average occupancy per apartment for each municipality. Similarly, the number of workers was estimated based on the number of employees in each activity within the area. To quantify noise levels, CERN collaborated with expert companies to conduct background noise measurements as part of the FCC environmental initial state analysis. Noise levels were recorded separately for day and night during different time periods. These background noise measurements are crucial for assessing if the additional noise generated by construction and operation activities is relevant or not. Subsequently, the FCC-ee noise levels during construction and operation near-surface sites were modelled by CERN experts, leveraging past measurements from CERN for the HL-LHC construction and LHC operation.

After accounting for commonly used mitigation measures at construction sites in inhabited areas, the expected noise levels are estimated to be 45 dBA at a distance of 100 m and 40 dBA at 200 m. These expected noise levels were then compared to the background noise levels at each site, as only the cost associated with the additional noise caused by the FCC-ee is considered for monetization purposes. The noise during operation, thanks to some mitigation measures, remains well below the 40dB threshold, both during the day and at night.

Table 22: Amount of noise expected in the main construction sites after accounting for commonly used mitigation measures.

SITE	ACOUSTIC MEASUREMENT POINT – L90	CONSTRUCTION NOISE [DB]	OPERATION NOISE [DB]	
			7h-22h	22h-7h
PA, Ferney-Voltaire	PA-PF01 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
	PA-PF03 (300m)	40.0	26.0	19.0
	PA-PF02 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
PB, Presinge (CH)	Point 3 (100m)	45.0	19.0	14.0
PD, Nangy	PD-PF48 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
	PD-PF47 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
PF, Éteaux	PF-PF38 (200m)	40.0	16.0	11.0
	PF-PF40 (200m)	45.0	19.0	14.0
	PF-PF43 (200m)	40.0	15.0	9.0
PH, Marlioz	PH-PF25 (100m)	45.0	35.0	34.0
	PH-PF28 (200m)	40.0	32.0	31.0
PL, Challex	PL-PF11 (200m)	40.0	32.0	31.0
	PL-PF22 (300m)	40.0	30.0	29.0

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

The health effects of noise are generally considered relevant only above certain thresholds. This threshold varies depending on the guidelines adopted, as there is no consensus at the international level. More conservative estimates set the threshold at 40dB²¹, while other agencies place it at 45dB or higher²².

The number of individuals affected by noise within a 100-meter radius of PH Marlioz and PB Presinge — the only two sites where construction noise is expected to have an impact exceeding 40dB — is 19. Since all these individuals are residents, it is assumed that they will spend 70% of their time at home (similar to the assumption made for radiation exposure), resulting in an estimate of around 13 people exposed to the noise.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

For monetisation purposes, only those sites where a significant increase in the level of noise (+5 dB L90²³) is expected and the 45dB threshold is surpassed (see the red cells in Table 22) were considered. As illustrated in the previous section, in most cases, the mitigation measures are expected to reduce the background noise. In a few cases, the expected increase in noise levels before and after construction operation is negligible. Concerning operation activities, the mitigation measures are expected to always

²¹ See [21] in Reference section.

²² See [22 and 23] in Reference section.

²³ Unit of measure of noise: it measures the amount of noise exceeded 90% of the time during the measurement period.

reduce noise emissions to levels below 40 dB. For this reason, the noise emitted during the operation phase is not taken into account for monetization purposes.

The monetary value for noise was taken from a technical note on the social cost of construction noise from the French Ministry of Ecological Transition²⁴. This note specifically addresses construction-related noise within the French context, and it includes a lower threshold for measuring effects, down to levels below 50 dB, unlike most other studies. The note relies on the literature and proposes different monetary values dependent on noise levels which is applicable to any construction site. It does so by estimating first an annual cost (€₂₀₁₈2,620) related to a loss of well-being for an exposed individual, which is the result of applying a 2% disability coefficient to the value of a year of healthy life set at €₂₀₁₈131,000²⁵. The final value is then obtained by multiplying the annual cost by the number of people exposed to each level of noise by using the dose-response curves for annoyance shown in Figure 14.

The noise from construction sites, especially during activities like demolition or heavy machinery operation, generates both low-frequency noise (e.g., engine sounds) and high-frequency noise (e.g., hammering). This noise is often intermittent and can create peaks in sound levels. The construction noise is therefore considered to have similarities to both road and rail traffic noise, as both sources also generate significant, varying noise levels. For this reason, the midpoint between road and rail traffic noise externality values is chosen to reflect the varying nature of construction noise. In particular, at 45dB, the loudest construction site of FCC-ee, the cost of annoyance from road traffic is €₂₀₁₈208, while for rail, it is €₂₀₁₈88. Taking the midpoint results in obtaining a value of €₂₀₁₈148, or €₂₀₂₄185.37.

Figure 14: Dose-response curves for annoyance caused by transport noise (road, rail, air)

Annoyed persons in % vs Noise in dB(A) Lden²⁶

Source: Bruitparif, d'après OMS (2018)²⁷

Results

The €₂₀₂₄185.37 figure, which is obtained by multiplying the number of exposed individuals for a given site by the cost of annoyance per exposed person, represents the cost of noise per year of construction.

²⁴Le coût des nuisances sonores des chantiers: quelle intégration dans les évaluations socio-économiques de projets?

²⁵ See [24] in Reference section.

²⁶ The Lden (Level day evening night) is a weighted average of noise levels over 24 hours, adjusted for sensitivity to noise during three periods (6 a.m.–6 p.m., 6 p.m.–10 p.m., 10 p.m.–6 a.m.).

²⁷ https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/publications/thema_essentiel_17_le_cout_des_nuisances_sonores_des_chantiers_quelle_integrer_dans_les_evaluations_socio_economiques_de_projets_mars_2022.pdf

Multiplying the number of exposed persons by the annual cost per exposed person generates a yearly cost of around € 2,462, which, multiplied by the entire construction period, results in a total cost of around € 24,616 (or CHF 23,449). The discounted figure is instead around € 17,008 (or CHF 16,202).

Table 23: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED
Baseline	16,202	23,449

Source: Authors

3.5. Ecosystem services loss

Introduction

The FCC project involves the construction of buildings and roads on predominantly agricultural and forested land. Consequently, the implementation of the project will result in [changes to land use](#) and activities conducted on it, thereby [impacting existing biodiversity and ecosystems](#). While the integration of biodiversity and ecosystem services analysis into socio-economic evaluations remains a relatively limited practice, there is growing consensus on their importance both in France²⁸, and at the international level²⁹. Accordingly, in the context of this study, the [negative externalities](#) arising from the [loss of ecosystems' services value](#) due to the implementation of the FCC project have been evaluated.

Over 92% of the projected area presently reserved for the project is in France and 8% in Switzerland. France's Legal Framework mandates compulsory measures to compensate for forest clearance as well as for agricultural economy losses of a territory³⁰ (Swiss law is comparatively stricter for forest protection, but presently, no forest clearance is planned on Swiss land). Additionally, in France, the Environmental Code, which focuses on biodiversity protection, requires the application of the "[Avoid-Reduce-Compensate](#)"³¹ (ERC) sequence during the design phase of any project impacting biodiversity (the principles of agricultural and forestry compensation do not fall under the Environmental Code but are governed respectively by the Rural and Maritime Fishing Code and the Forestry Code. Financial measures are possible in these cases, unlike biodiversity compensation, which must necessarily be carried out in kind). To implement this approach, CERN commissioned a study based on an ecological expert's judgement and IBP score attribution³² to assess biodiversity presence on the target land. The study mapped and categorized the areas by the following type: very high/high/medium/low/very low biodiversity risk³³. The results are available [here](#).

As the ERC approach requires ecological equivalence (=biodiversity gains at least equal to the biodiversity losses caused by the project), the residual impact on biodiversity to consider in the Cost Benefit Analysis is expected to be negligible once the design of the project is finalised (compensatory measures are currently under planning) and, at least [some of the ecosystem services losses are expected to offset as a](#)

²⁸ See [\[25 and 26\]](#) in Reference section.

²⁹ See [\[27\]](#) (Chapter 5) and [\[28\]](#) (Chapter 13) in Reference section.

³⁰ See [\[29\]](#) in Reference section.

³¹ <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/eviter-reduire-compenser-impacts-lenvironnement>

³² <https://www.cnpf.fr/ibp-index-biodiversity-potential>

³³ No "protected areas" were mapped within the project's perimeter

result. That said, in the context of this study, the negative externalities were assessed based on the information currently available on the project design.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 - Quantifying the negative externalities from ecosystem service loss

The quantification of negative externalities from ecosystem service loss is based on the estimation of impacted areas and the selection of ecosystems' services for which loss can be reasonably quantified.

The **total area reserved for the project**—the land planned to be acquired by CERN³⁴ — is **76.2 hectares**, with 70.3 ha in France and 5.9 ha in Switzerland.

CERN has commissioned two specific studies to external experts to characterise the target land: a forest study finalized in September 2024 (available [here](#)) and an agricultural study (whose preliminary results are available [here](#)).

Of the reserved area, **18%** was classified as forest land and **82%** was classified as agricultural land, including cultivated areas and non-cultivated areas such as meadows and land used for grazing or hay production³⁵.

Table 24: Total area (cadastral area) reserved for the project (hectares). Breakdown by site, location and type of land

	TOTAL AREA	of which in France	of which in Switzerland	of which agricultural land	cultivated	non cultivated	of which forest land
PA	13.9	13.9		13.9	13.9	0	0
PB	5.9		5.9	5.9	5.9	0	0
PD	11.5	11.5		11.5	0	11.5	0
PF	8.3	8.3		8.3	0	8.3	0
PG	10.8	10.8		8.4	4.3	4.1	2.4
PH	11.3	11.3		0.8	0	0.8	10.5
PJ	8.9	8.9		8.9	8.9	0	0
PL	5.6	5.6		4.9	4.9	0	0.7
Total	76.2	70.3	5.9	62.6	37.9	24.7	13.6

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication data

The FCC-related project activities which will be conducted in the reserved area³⁶ are the following:

- Construction of **buildings**
- Construction of **roads**
- Creation of **green buffers** around the buildings (tree planting and meadows)
- **Re-naturalization** areas (wetlands improvement).

³⁴ The FCC project does not develop on land already owned by CERN; all land will be acquired.

³⁵ Constructed area is marginal and made by three houses and 0.3ha of asphalted area.

³⁶ Compensation measures also include interventions outside the reserved area, such as agricultural land restoration and reforestation activities designated by local authorities in other locations out of the project's perimeter.

Buildings, roads and green buffers will be fenced, while re-naturalization areas will remain on the reserved area but unfenced. The fenced area covered by project interventions is 53.2 ha in the baseline scenario and 47.8 ha in the optimized one. The optimized scenario, currently under investigation, envisions a reduced fenced surface, less soil sealing and more green buffers. In both the baseline and optimized scenarios, 7.8 hectares of naturalization areas are included. The total area impacted by the project's interventions is thus 61.0 hectares (55.6 hectares optimized). The difference between the reserved area and the project's intervention area is made by the sum of portions of cadastral plots reserved for the project but not covered by interventions as well as access plots and access roads.

Table 25: Project's planned interventions by type (hectares). Baseline and optimized scenario

	Fenced surface Baseline scenario -			Fenced surface Optimized scenario -			Non fenced surface
	Total fenced area	of which buildings and roads	of which green buffers	Total fenced area	of which buildings and roads	of which green buffers	Re-naturalization areas
PA	8.9	5.3	3.6	8.9	2.9	6.0	5
PB	5.3	3.2	2.1	4.9	2.2	2.7	0
PD	4.9	6.0	-1.137	4.5	3.7	0.8	0
PF	4.1	3.1	1.0	4.8	2.0	2.8	2.8
PG	10.1	5.7	4.4	10.1	4.1	6.0	0
PH	8.2	6.6	1.6	4.4	4.4	0.0	0
PJ	6.1	5.8	0.3	5.3	3.8	1.4	0
PL	5.6	4.2	1.4	4.9	2.6	2.3	0
Total	53.2	39.9	13.3	47.8	25.9	22.0	7.8

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

As a consequence of the project's planned interventions, changes in land use will occur on the majority of the cadastral area reserved. The changes are reported in the table below.

³⁷ To be ignored. The site was beyond the foreseen available space however a few buildings were put on the induced project area

Table 26: Areas (cadastral) affected by land use/destination change (hectares). Baseline and optimized scenario

	BASELINE SCENARIO	OPTIMIZED SCENARIO
Forest land → Constructed area	8.2	5.1
Agricultural land → Constructed area	31.7	20.8
Agricultural land cultivated → Meadow	5.1	10.1
Agricultural land → Tree plantation	7.7	15.2
Agricultural land → Wetland	7.8	7.8

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

Any change in land use can potentially result in a variation in the value of the ecosystem services provided. The adopted approach focuses on the most significant impact in terms of hectares affected or the expected degree of variation of the ecosystem's service value.

Ecosystem's services classification here adopted is based on the one introduced by TEEB – the Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity – Initiative in 2010 and then taken up in existing literature.

- **Provisioning services** (which are the products obtained from ecosystems, including food, fresh water, fuel, fibre, biochemicals, and genetic resources). The FCC project implementation will lead to the loss of provisioning services due to the cessation of agricultural and forestry activities on the **total cadastral area planned to be acquired**³⁸. As a result, raw materials and products (wood, agricultural products) from these areas will no longer be available.
- **Regulating & habitat services** (which are the benefits obtained from the ecosystem's natural regulating process, including climate regulation, carbon sequestration, disease regulation, water regulation, etc.), including **biodiversity**³⁹, which is in the literature often considered a supporting service, as it underpins the functioning of ecosystems (greater biodiversity generally translates into enhanced ecosystem resilience and a broader range of ecosystem services). The FCC project implementation will result in a change of land destinations (see

³⁸ No agricultural activity will be conducted by CERN on the plots acquired for the project's construction, even if no actual construction will take place on them. The agricultural space currently used for cultivation will be converted into uncultivated meadows, with no active agricultural activity

³⁹ See for example Table 5-1: List of ecosystem services, [27].

- Table 26). The most relevant regulating & habitat services loss derives from **soil sealing** due to construction activities.
- **Cultural services** (which relate to the experiences that people enjoy as a result of interactions with nature (e.g. recreation), as well as more intangible pleasures arising from knowledge about the existence of nature or its spiritual value). In the context of FCC, they were not considered for two main reasons: i) no significant recreational activity is currently present or planned on the land, and ii) the high level of discretion and variability (greater than the average of other ecosystem services) in value attribution of this services in existing in studies and literature.

Table 27: Quantified ecosystem’s services loss by main type of ecosystem’s services and land changes

	PROVISIONING SERVICES	REGULATING AND HABITAT SERVICES
Forest land → Constructed area	✓	✓
Agricultural land → Constructed area	✓	✓
Agricultural land cultivated→ Meadow	✓	-
Agricultural land → Tree plantation	✓	(benefit)*
Agricultural land → Wetland	✓	(benefit)*

Source: Authors; *see Section 5.3

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The monetisation approach was differentiated for provisioning and regulating/habitat services. However, in both cases, reference values for ecosystem services were expressed in EUR2024/ha/year.

Monetization of provisioning services

For **forest land** provisioning services, a baseline value of 294 EUR/ha/year was adopted. This is the average **technical value** determined based on the forest study⁴⁰ conducted on the reserved project’s area by external experts through sampling and field visits (the values range from a minimum of 11 EUR/ha/year and a maximum value of 632 EUR/ha/year in the analysed surface). This value accounts for the soil and the actualized harvesting potential, including the value of trees that have not yet reached maturity for use⁴¹.

For **agricultural land** provisioning services, a baseline value of 3.649 EUR/ha/year was adopted (the values range from a minimum of 1.515 EUR/ha/year and a maximum value of 9.082 EUR/ha/year in the analysed surface). This is the average value of **agricultural loss** estimated in the agricultural study, which was based on a direct investigation of the farming activities present in the area reserved for the project. This value accounts for the direct and indirect (supply chain) loss of agricultural production, including cereal production and other cultivations, forage, etc.

⁴⁰ The yearly metric was derived dividing the estimated average EUR/ha value found in the study by 30, assuming this is the lifespan needed for a full regeneration of forest.

⁴¹ Land acquisition costs (both for forest and agricultural land) are also included in CAPEX, thus generating a double counting issue. Still, we considered this double counting tolerable in the context of a conservative approach.

Monetization of regulating and habitat services

A value transfer approach was adopted applying the monetary value of the ecosystem service estimated in another context to the FCC context. Despite being aware of all the limitations inherent to this approach, given the complexity of ecosystem services functioning and their subsequent valorisations, it was chosen for its feasibility among those indicated by international guidelines for ecosystem service valuation⁴². Still, the monetization of services should be interpreted with prudence as demonstrated by the high variabilities of metrics from literature and case studies.

The source adopted to retrieve the necessary data to implement the value transfer approach was the ESVD database⁴³, which collects around ten thousand evaluations worldwide and across ecosystems based on a wide range of methodologies. The database provides values broken down by biome and by ecosystem service. In practice, the pertinent biome (temperate forest, intensive land use/cropland, wetlands) and geographical area (Europe) were selected, and the values of relevant regulating and habitat services for which sufficient data was available (with a minimum threshold of at least 10 observations) were retrieved. Descriptive statistics included mean, median, min and max values. Median values were chosen as a reference⁴⁴.

- **Regulating and supporting services of forest ecosystem** (inc. Air quality regulation, climate regulation, and C-sequestration): 533 EUR/ha/year (min 20 EUR/ha/year, max 6,625 EUR/ha/year)
- **Regulating and supporting services of agricultural land** (inc. Air quality regulation, climate regulation, and C-sequestration): 574 EUR/ha/year (min 8 EUR/ha/year, max 4,854 EUR/ha/year)

Results

The table below presents the total externality from ecosystem services loss due to the FCC project implementation. It was calculated by applying the estimated per hectare ecosystem provisioning and regulating/habitat services' loss to the impacted land area starting from the year the land-use change occurred (assumed to be one year ahead of the project's construction) and continuing until the end of the period. In the best-case scenario and worst-case scenario the lower bound and higher bound values retrieved for monetization were respectively adopted.

Table 28: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024)

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED
Baseline	4,144,449	7,638,426
Best-case scenario	1,509,507	2,733,810
Worst case scenario	13,486,313	25,691,824

Source: Authors

⁴² See for example: [30] or [31]. International guidelines suggest also other valorisation methods including primary study, modelling platform, and value transfer functions which we discarded because of their complexity and/or lack of data.

⁴³ This database (<https://www.esvd.net>) was initially developed for the TEEB - The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity in 2010.

⁴⁴ The values retrieved were expressed in int\$/year 2020. They were converted into EUR using PPP conversion factors (source: World Bank) and transformed in 2024 values by using GDP deflator (source: IMF).

3.6. Traffic-related externalities

Introduction

For the construction of the tunnel, approximately 8 million m³ of excavated material will need to be extracted and disposed of. While some of this material will be reused on-site, a portion will require transportation by truck to sorting facilities, quarries, and other destinations. The objective of this chapter is to estimate the externalities associated with pollution, GHG emissions, and congestion from the trucks used to transport the material.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the traffic-related externalities

CERN provided⁴⁵ traffic estimates for trucks transporting excavated material. The document included an initial estimation of the quantity of excavated material and the different types of trucks used. Quantities were then adjusted to reflect the updated data used for the quantification of excavated materials management costs.

CERN outlined four transport alternatives:

- 4-axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 18 tonnes and a capacity of 12 m³.
- 5-axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 24 tonnes and a capacity of 17 m³.
- (3+2) axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 24 tonnes and a capacity of 24 m³.
- (2+3) axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 25 tonnes and a capacity of 24 m³.

Considering a weight of 2 tonnes per m³ of excavated soil, the maximum capacity for each type of truck can be calculated. This is necessary to determine the number of trucks needed to transport the material. According to the type of terrain (polluted, non-polluted, depolluted) and the country of destination, a specific distance is assigned.

The three scenarios have been constructed as follows:

- Worst-case scenario: In this scenario, French-polluted material is depolluted on-site, and trucks travel 65 km (round trip) to transport the material to quarries, while French-polluted material travels 35 km to quarries for disposal. Swiss material travels 70 km for type B material, 15 km for type E material, and 15 km for depolluted material.⁴⁶ 4-axle trucks are considered.
- Best-case scenario: French depolluted and non-polluted material travels 25 km to the nearest quarries. Swiss material is treated the same way as in the worst-case scenario.⁴⁷ (2+3)-axle trucks are considered.
- Baseline scenario: Similar to what is done for the management of excavation material cost, the baseline is an average of scenarios B and C. 5-axle trucks are considered.

⁴⁵ On December 5th, 2024.

⁴⁶ The material quantities and distances for this scenario equals those considered for scenario B in the quantification of excavated materials management costs (see box 2).

⁴⁷ The material quantities and distances for this scenario equals those considered for scenario C in the quantification of excavated materials management costs (see box 2).

Table 29: Km travelled by truck (one way) in the reference scenarios

SCENARIO	MATERIAL TYPE	FRANCE	SWITZERLAND
Worse case (i.e. Scenario B in the quantification of excavated materials management costs)	Polluted material	-	70 (type B ⁴⁸)
			15 (type E)
	Non-polluted material	35	15 (type A)
	Depolluted material	65	-
Best-case (i.e. scenario C in the quantification of excavated materials management costs)	Polluted material	-	70 (type B)
			15 (type E)
	Non-polluted material	25	15 (type A)
	Depolluted material	25	-

Source: CERN

An assessment of the congestion-related externalities was also attempted. Using CERN's data on daily traffic near the extraction points and assuming a road capacity of 15,000 vehicles per day (the capacity of a road with one lane in each direction), it is possible to roughly determine whether the additional trucks on the road result in an increase in the volume-to-capacity (v/c) ratio. The v/c ratio is a measure of road congestion, representing the ratio of the actual traffic volume to the maximum capacity of the road. Based on [22], four levels of congestion can be identified:

- A v/c ratio below 0.8 indicates no congestion
- A v/c ratio between 0.8 and 1 indicates a near-capacity road
- A v/c ratio between 1 and 1.2 indicates congestion
- A v/c ratio above 1.2 indicates overcapacity

The table below shows the incremental number of vehicles caused by the transport of excavated material (using a passenger car equivalent of 2) compared to current traffic levels to identify changes in the v/c ratio. Examining the roads around the nine extraction sites (the eight sites and the injector), the additional trucks, in all scenarios, do not cause a significant increase in the v/c ratio that would change the traffic condition from one category to another. Therefore, based on the data available, no congestion effects are identified.

⁴⁸ Categories A, B and E correspond to the type of landfill that can accept the material, with each category indicating the level of contamination, starting from A (the least polluted). For further details, refer to the Ordinance on the Avoidance and the Disposal of Waste, 4th December 2015 (Swiss Federal Office).

Table 30: Congestion state of roads around the extraction sites before and during construction

SCENARIO	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL	INJ.
Daily traffic before construction	7,803	5,918	20,475	11,331	13,681	1,709	13,954	3,380	7,803
v/c ratio before construction	0.52	0.39	1.37	0.76	0.91	0.11	0.93	0.23	0.52
Daily traffic during construction	8,342	5,976	20,973	11,396	14,215	1,831	14,458	3,474	7,851
v/c ratio during construction	0.56	0.40	1.40	0.76	0.95	0.12	0.96	0.23	0.52

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 2 – Monetisation**

After determining the km*veh in each scenario and knowing the total weight of cargo per truck, the total cost of air pollution can be estimated using values from [22] (expressed in €-cent per tkm) for each truck category.

The km*veh estimate also allows for the calculation of GHG emissions associated with the transport of excavated material. The emission values, expressed in €-cent per tkm, were also taken from [22] and followed the same assumptions used for air pollution.

Values are converted to CHF (2024) and discounted, given that they are distributed evenly for 8 years starting 2033, the beginning of construction.

Table 31: Unit cost of traffic pollution and GHG emissions (€-cent per t*km, 2016)

SCENARIO	POLLUTION	GHG EMISSIONS
4 axle truck	0.18	1.27
5 axle truck	0.09	0.75
3 + 2 axle	0.08	0.74
2 + 3 axle	0.08	0.7

Source: Authors based on [22]

Results

The table below presents the results of the traffic-related externalities.

Table 32: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024)

	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED	TOTAL DISCOUNTED
Baseline scenario		
Pollution	1,175,942	834,336
GHG emissions	9,799,518	6,952,801
Total	10,975,461	7,787,137
Worst-case scenario		
Pollution	2,778,669	1,971,478
GHG emissions	19,605,051	13,909,870
Total	22,383,720	15,881,348
Best-case scenario		
Pollution	855,600	607,052
GHG emissions	7,914,301	5,615,231
Total	8,769,901	6,222,283

Source: Authors

4. CORE BENEFITS

Starting from [1], we updated and expanded the quantified impacts.

4.1. The value of scientific production

Introduction

This benefit stems from the traditional idea – [10, 11, 12] – of “knowledge push”, according to which research infrastructures generate scientific publications and similar products either directly or via their users. These are cited and eventually become part of a new body of knowledge. That body of knowledge later finds conscious or unconscious recognition within a broader research community and society. Final recipients of the knowledge generated may further translate it into economic benefits or apply it to societal problem-solving efforts.

The benefit has been revised to account for changes in the project’s design (increasing from two experiments to four) and to incorporate more accurate estimates of the research effort attributable to FCC-ee, updating the preliminary analysis previously carried out by [1]. The estimation focused on the first stages of the “knowledge push” impacts, such as on the *scientific outputs* which are likely to be generated by *scientists* and *post-docs* involved in the accelerators, infrastructure, and experiments.

Estimation

For the purpose of this analysis, we considered scientific products, any kind of research product directly produced by the FCC-ee scientific community and cited by the research community. Scientific products considered in the analysis are therefore not limited to articles published in peer-reviewed journals, but they include a diversity of outputs, such as:

- Articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals,
- Working papers, non-peer-reviewed articles (e.g. made available on the CERN Document Server, Zenodo, ArXiv and dedicated open-access libraries),
- Preprints (e.g. published on ArXiv and Zenodo),
- Conference proceedings,
- Conference and workshop presentations and posters,
- Scientific and technical books,
- Chapters in edited scientific and technical books.

For long-term research programs like the FCC-ee, it is crucial to identify the stages of research activity where scientific products are generated. This analysis categorizes scientific products into three distinct tiers:

- **Tier 0 scientific products (P0):** they are produced by scientists, engineers and other researchers who actively participate in the research programme. They serve as a “corpus” for the creation of further knowledge and science products. These products capture the knowledge acquired during the design, construction and operation phases of the FCC-ee.
- **Tier 1 science products (P1):** they cite P0 products.
- **Tier 2 science products (P2):** they cite P1 products.

Although additional tiers of scientific products could be identified, this analysis is limited to the first two citation streams (P1 and P2). The contributions of further tiers decline progressively, making their overall impact relatively minor in the context of the value estimation.

The estimation of this benefit relied on the following steps:

➤ **STEP 1 - Estimation of P0 publications:**

The estimation of P0 publication regarded both the number and the distribution over time,

- (i) The scale of the number of scientific products⁴⁹, as well as the distribution by type (peer-reviewed paper, magazine article, conference proceeding, etc.), was based on the LHC historical data from 1990-2021, as reported by [2].
- (ii) The shape of scientific production was based on the LEP trend, similar to the approach followed by [1]. Therefore, there will be a long period of scientific production with small peaks immediately after an increase in the precision levels (i.e., radio frequency (RF) updates of FCC-ee). According to information shared by CERN in the framework of [1], the physics that will be conducted on the FCC-ee collider will be qualitatively more similar to what was done with LEP and Tevatron. The FCC-ee experiments will provide more and more precise measurements of phenomena that will certainly be observed with high frequency, such as Higgs particles.

Similarly to [1], the team also considered a timeline which covers the entire time horizon of FCC-ee and beyond, based on the assumptions that data analysis will continue for some time after the FCC-ee ends operations. The production curve declines though quickly after the end of the operation, following the trend of the previously observed pattern at the LEP.

The figure below illustrates the trend of P0 publications for FCC-ee over the period 2024–2083 based on these assumptions. Specifically, a total of 34,397 P0 products were estimated for the period 2024–2064, increasing to 38,008 by 2083, based on extrapolation from [2].

⁴⁹ In [1], the number of P0 products were estimated on the basis of historical data from three other high-energy physics projects and the respective experiment collaborations linked to these research programmes: (i) US DOE Fermilab Tevatron programme and the CDF and D0 experiment collaborations, (ii) CERN LEP programme with the ALEPH, DELPHI, L3 and OPAL experiment collaborations, (iii) CERN LHC with the ATLAS, ALICE, CMS and LHCb experiment collaborations. Historical data on scientific products over the period 1993-2022 were retrieved by Springer-Nature team for FCCIS using the INSPIRE database. Data on the P0 products were obtained by considering the products authored by any of these collaborations, as recorded in INSPIRE. For the purpose of the update of this benefit, the Team only consider historical data related to LHC given the pattern of FCC-ee with 4 experiments.

Figure 15 Number of P0 scientific products related to FCC-ee

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 2 - Estimate the number of scientific products citing P0 products (P1, P2) and the number of citations (Q0, Q1):**

Similarly to [1], the Team estimated the number of P1 and P2 products that can be attributed to the FCC-ee P0 products and the number of citations that P0 and P1 products receive (Q0 and Q1) by assuming the same trend observed for the LHC. In particular, scientific products have very different characteristics in terms of number, level of citations and co-authorship in the two phases of construction and, later, operation. More specifically:

- The number of P1 and P2 products over time is estimated using the yearly trend of P1/P0 and P2/P0 ratios from the LHC program. On average, each P0 product generates 1.3 P1 products over the entire construction and operation period—0.6 during construction and 2.3 during operation. Similarly, each P0 product generates an average of 3.7 P2 products, with 1.5 occurring during the construction phase and 6.0 during the operation phase.
- Similarly, each P0 is expected to receive an average of 6.3 citations (Q0/P0), with a lower average of 1.3 during the construction phase and a higher average of 11.6 during the operation phase. In turn, P1 papers generated by a single P0 receive an average of 19 citations, with the highest levels occurring during the construction phase.

The following Table summarises the parameters used for the quantification:

Table 33: Parameters for the estimation of citing papers (average value)

Ratios of products and citations	LHC SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTS		
	Construction 1993-2007	Operation 2008-2021	Average for the period 1993-2021
P1/P0	0.6	2.0	1.3
P2/P0	1.5	6.0	3.7
Q0/P0	1.3	11.6	6.3
Q1/P0	2.8	36.5	19.1

Source: Authors based on [1] **Note:** Historical data from 1993 to 2021 were considered.

The following Table provides an overview of the total number of FCC-ee scientific products:

Table 34: Total number of FCC-ee scientific products

	Total 2024-2064	Total 2024-2083
P0	34,397	38,008
P1	80,189	91,343
P2	457,978	526,782
Q0 (number of times P0 are cited by P1)	387,964	453,323
Q1 (number of times P1 are cited by P2)	2,318,087	2,703,048

Source: Authors

Figure 16 Expected distribution of FCC-ee scientific products over time – P0, P1, P2 (2024-2083)

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimating the value of P0 publications:**

In line with existing literature [1,6] and the approach applied in the socio-economic analysis of the LHC and HL-LHC [1; 8], the quantitative estimation of the value of scientific products is based on the Marginal Cost of Production (MCP). This approach is grounded in the economic concepts of "opportunity cost" and the "value of time." When a scientist chooses to dedicate time to activities such as writing an article, downloading, reading, or citing someone else's work, it involves a "lost opportunity" to allocate that time to the next best professional activity, such as conducting additional research or teaching. As a result, the (minimum) value of a scientific product can be approximated by multiplying the estimated time spent by individuals involved in its production by their average hourly salaries. This does not include the future value of utility for society of knowledge per se as embodied in a publication, because this is ex-ante unknown.

For each considered publication tier (P0, P1, P2), the value is made of two components: the social value of producing new information *per se* plus a social value attributed to the degree of influence of that piece of knowledge on the scientific community. The social value is captured by the number of scientific productions and valued through the marginal production cost for each tier (P0, P1, P2). The influence is reflected by the number of people that consume the scientific product reflected by the number of citations. Using citations as a measure of the significance of a scientific product is an imperfect but widely accepted approach to capture the social recognition and esteem that the scientific community acknowledges in the paper.

For this estimation, the team relied on the MCP model suggested by [2], which considers the number of authors of each paper and the productivity of each of the contributing authors in the calculation. The formula used to calculate the unit cost of production is detailed in the box below.

Box 3 The marginal cost of production model

$$MPC_{f,t} = MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c + MPC_{pub_t} = \left(\frac{w_{res_{j,f,t}} * h_{res_{j,f,t}}}{y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)} \right) * n_t + MPC_{pub_t}$$

Where

$MPC_{f,t}$ is the average marginal cost of producing a generic scientific publication in the scientific field f at time t

$MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ is the average marginal cost of doing research in that field.

$w_{res_{j,f,t}}$ denotes the average annual salary of the j -th author(s) doing research with $j = 1, \dots, n, \dots, N$;

$h_{res_{j,f,t}}$ denotes their average share of working time dedicated to research and it ranges from 0 to 100%.

MPC_{pub_t} reflects other publication production costs

In this model, the author(s)' productivity is a monotonically increasing function of the (average) number of co-authors (n_t). The number of authors per paper is then used as a scaling factor for the term $MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ to incorporate co-authorship into the equation. The interpretation of $MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ is this: given the share of time allocated to research ($h_{res_{j,f,t}}$), co-authorship reduces each author's individual contribution to a paper but it increases productivity, allowing for more articles to be signed in a given period. The term in brackets $\left(\frac{w_{res_{j,f,t}} * h_{res_{j,f,t}}}{y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)} \right)$ represents single-author publications and, therefore, requires adjustment for the number of co-authors. The functional form of $y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)$ is unknown a priori and may vary by scientific fields, time period, and other factors, as collaboration practices differ across disciplines and evolve over time.

Source: Authors based on [2]

The application of the formula described above required the following ingredients:

- **The average annual gross salary of personnel expected to produce P0 Products:** Based on evidence from interviews, it was assumed that only Scientists and Postdoctoral Researchers—working on both accelerators and infrastructures as well as experiments—contribute to authoring scientific publications. Using this assumption, we calculated a weighted average annual gross salary for these personnel, distinguishing between those managed by CERN and those managed by other institutions (see Section 3.1 and the table below for an overview). For scientists involved in experiments, assumptions were made regarding their salaries to account for the time they allocate to research activities and specifically to FCC-ee-related work (see details in the point below).

Table 35: Estimation of the average annual gross salary of P0 authors

Personnel working on accelerator and infrastructure and experiments	Total number	% managed by CERN	% managed other institutions	Gross annual salary CERN	Gross annual salary Other institutions	Weighted average salary (CHF, 2024, undiscounted)
<i>Scientists</i>	37,103	14%	86%	211,915	20,344*	58,542
<i>Post docs</i>	68,143	15%	85%	84,318	67,454	

Source: Authors **Note:** *The average salary for scientists managed by other institutions is estimated to be CHF 169,532. Based on the assumption that this group spends only 55% of their time on research activities and, within that, dedicates an average of 22% of their research time to FCC-ee, the yearly salary share was 12%

- **Time dedicated to research and FCC-ee:** Among the categories assumed to contribute to signing papers, the team considered that scientists and post-doctoral researchers working on the accelerators dedicate 100% of their time to research and to the FCC-ee project. Similarly, post-doctoral researchers working on the experiments also spend 100% of their time on research activities. For scientists working on experiments and managed by other institutions, however, evidence from interviews confirmed that they allocate only a portion of their time to a specific research project, hence to FCC-ee-related work. The team relied on assumptions from [1], which are based on Nature's 2016 Jobs Survey⁵⁰. This survey indicates that the average academic researcher spends approximately 55% of their time conducting scientific research and writing articles, while the remaining time is allocated to administrative tasks, teaching, data storage, and writing grant applications. Consistent with these findings, the team assumed that 55% of the FCC-ee project's scientific personnel time is dedicated to scientific research and the development of scientific products. Additionally, it was assumed that only a portion of their research time is dedicated to FCC-ee-related products. Based on [2], this was estimated to be an average of 22% over the considered time horizon. As a result, only a share of the salary rate was applied to this category. These assumptions ensure that the estimations of personnel costs and their contributions to generating benefits are consistent.
- The **average marginal cost of publishing:** this parameter was set at EUR 311 PPS in line with [2].
- The **productivity function** $y_{rest}(n_t)$: according to [2] productivity range per author is a relatively small number of papers signed per year (**often 6 or lower**) for papers with few authors, but it dramatically increases over time and with the number of authors (**up to 30-60**) signed paper per year.

⁵⁰ <https://www.chemistryworld.com/careers/time-after-time-how-academic-researchers-spend-their-working-life/2500016.article>.

- **Number of authors:** the team analysed the distribution of authors for the 34,397 LHC-related P0 products published between 1990 and 2021, excluding rare outliers such as papers with more than 3,000 authors. The analysis revealed that 91% of the papers—31,150 in total—were authored by 1 to 100 authors, while 9% - 3,247 papers - were authored by more than 100 authors. Among the latter, some papers had author counts up to 3000 and beyond. For scientific products with a very high number of co-authors, the use of the marginal cost of production method to value their economic value can be misleading. In fact, as confirmed by interviews, the number of scientists actually drafting those papers remains limited to 20-25 as a maximum, the remaining being members of the collaboration whose contribution is different, such as control of data-taking or review activities rather than scientific output production. The magnitude and value of these (more indirect) contribution to individual scientific products can be hard to establish and would require ad hoc methodologies and empirical analysis. However, given the assumption that 100% of post-doc time is directly devoted to FCC research (which is probably an overestimation), these 'background' activities are already considered.
- **Valuation rule:** Given the above-mentioned uncertainty about the actual contributions of authors, a simple shortcut rule is needed:
 - For papers with 1 to 100 authors, we assume that all contributors fully participated in the production of the scientific output, each contributing her/his time proportionally, based on their estimated productivity. Hence, if the 100th author is a post-doc who signs 6 papers per year, his contribution to such paper is 1/6 of her/his yearly gross salary. If the author is a scientist with the same productivity, it would on average be 1/6 of 12% of her/his gross salary (with a range going from 100% to zero).
 - For papers with more than 100 authors, whatever the total number of authors (usually reflecting the size of the collaborations or sub-sets of them), we cap the value to 100 actual contributing authors, with a time effort and value proportional to the corresponding productivity, as above. This is an upper bound for the number of actual contributing authors in terms of dedicated time and is a way to give the same value to the internal review process and additional activities beyond mere drafting within the collaborations.
 - At a later stage, uncertainty on the capping threshold can be dealt with Montecarlo simulations (e.g. with a cap at 25, suggested by some interviewed scientists, or using a percentage of the authors).

Based on the above parameters and applying the MCP formula suggested by [\[2\]](#), the Team calculated an **average unit production cost equal to 126,122 CHF** for the period 2024-2083, with wide variance below and over the threshold of actual authors. Therefore, this average should be interpreted primarily as a summary statistic, rather than a precise figure. Of the 34,397 publications considered, 90.6% are contributed by fewer than 100 authors. More notably, 80.2% of these publications (27,597) are contributed by an even smaller group of authors - fewer than 8 authors. The median value of the production costs associated to these publications - contributed by 8 authors - is approximately 18,700 CHF, a trend consistent with many other scientific fields.

➤ **STEP 4 - Estimating the value of P1 and P2 publications:**

The value of P1 and P2 products differs from the value of P0. Starting from the unit production value estimated for P0, the Team relied on similar assumptions adopted by [\[1\]](#). These assumptions can be summarised as follows:

- According to historical data based on LHC scientific production, **the average number of citations contained in P1 and P2 products is 50**. It means that 2% of the unit value of a scientific product (1/50) can be attributed to the P1 products. Nevertheless, some P0 products may provide a highly significant contribution to P1. For those highly influential P0, the Team assumed that up to one-third (such as 33%) of the value contained in the P1 product was influenced by the P0 product.
- The value of P2 products is estimated in a similar way. It is the total marginal cost of P1 paper production divided by the number of references that the paper contains. Its value is lower than P1 products because the initial input given by the P0 product is diluted at each new eave of knowledge production.
- Similarly to P0, also the unit production cost of P1 and P2 products change over time.
- Finally, the value of a citation (Q0 and Q1) is estimated by assuming an average of 3 hours necessary to produce the citation, i.e. reading the original paper, understanding it, and deciding how to cite it in the new paper. With an average annual salary of 58 542 CHF and assuming a total of 1,600 working hours per year, the value of a citation amounts to 110 CHF.

Results

The total value of scientific production is estimated by multiplying the number of P0, P1, and P2 scientific products and the Q0 and Q1 citations and their respective unit values. [The total undiscounted benefit of all estimated FCC-ee scientific products amounts to 6.5 CHF billion in the baseline scenario, which represents 2.8 CHF billion after applying the social discount rate of 2.8%](#). As the Table below shows, the largest share of the benefit (nearly 90%) is represented by the value of P0 scientific products generated by the scientists, engineers, and researchers directly involved in the FCC-ee project from its design phase until the end of operation and for some time beyond that.

[As a next step, the team will assume a lower and upper bounds scenario, which considers variations of certain inputs used for the calculation](#) (e.g. share of time dedicated to research, etc.), to determine their suitability and will revise them accordingly. Residual uncertainty will be dealt with in Montecarlo simulations.

Table 36: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024)

	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED	SHARE
P0 scientific products	2,542,936,009	5,831,401,438	90.4%
P1 scientific products (total)	117,359,181	288,833,542	4.2%
P2 scientific products	12,400,551	31,831,373	0.4%
(Q0) P1 citations	23,522,523	57,822,586	0.8%
(Q1) P2 citations	117,021,158	296,701,799	4.2%
Total	2,813,239,421	6,506,590,739	100.0%

Source: Authors

Figure 17 Time profile of the total value of scientific production – Baseline scenario (CHF)

Source: Authors

4.2. Human capital

Introduction

People are essential to the development and operation of research infrastructure. They conduct data analysis, design and build experiments, develop software, produce scientific and technical publications, test and qualify equipment, and create tools and methods for these tasks. They also perform laboratory work, identify issues, devise solutions, and maintain and repair scientific instruments, continually enhancing their performance throughout their lifecycle. Throughout their involvement in the project, these individuals acquire a diverse range of technical skills, improve their problem-solving abilities, learn teamwork, and develop management and communication capabilities. They also build social capital by gaining access to a broad network of contacts within the scientific community. Additionally, their direct participation in the activities of a highly respected research centre enhances their professional reputation. These effects collectively result in better job opportunities and a "premium" on their future salaries. This premium reflects the so-called "marginal⁵¹" salary increase gained by an early-stage researcher or engineer who works for a limited period of time at the research infrastructure, compared to a salary which would be earned without that specific work experience.

In the framework of this assignment, the benefit relates to the training and education effects of on-the-job training carried out during the FCC-ee lifetime for students and early-stage researchers. The benefit – as previously estimated – has been revised to account for changes in the project's design (increasing from two experiments to four) as well as revised assumptions.

Estimation

The estimation of this benefit relied on the following steps:

➤ STEP 1 - Estimating the number of people benefitting from the salary premium

As a first step of this estimation, the team calculated the number of people per year who are likely to benefit from the salary premium until the end of the FCC-ee operation phase. This number is a fraction of the total number of people reported in Section 3.1. Specifically, only students and early-career researchers, including post-doctoral employees, are considered to benefit from the salary premium, as no studies have been conducted for other professional groups. It is understood that this limitation may lead to an underestimate of the overall impact.

In line with [1], two criteria were considered to determine the fraction of people who benefit from a lifetime salary premium:

1. People younger than 30 years
2. People who spend at least one full year on the project and no longer than five years.

Historical human resources data covering the 1990-2023 period were analysed to estimate these two criteria. The following categories of contracts were not considered in the analysis:

- Personnel with an indefinite staff contract who stay at CERN for a long time;

⁵¹ In economics, the term "marginal" refers to the value change if the observed quantity is incremented by one unit.

- Corresponding associates and trainees (participating in an internship or other bilateral training programmes established with Member States), who typically stay for less than 1 year at CERN;
- Guest professors, who are typically older than 30 years old.

Table 37: Share of personnel under 30 years old and duration of stay at CERN by contract

CATEGORY	SHARE UNDER 30 YEARS OLD (AVERAGE 1990-2023)	AVERAGE DURATION OF STAY AT CERN (YEARS 1990-2023)
Staff with limited contract	1.87%	5
Fellow	54.00%	2.3
User	28.52%	3.9
Cooperation associate	31.34%	1.4
Project associate	34.65%	1.9
Scientific Associate	2.29%	1
Visiting Scientist	10.13%	1
Doctoral student	80.81%	2.8
Technical student	88.37%	1
Administrative student	83.30%	1
Apprentice	100.00%	3.44
Average	28.84%	3.79

Source: Authors' elaboration based on CERN historical HR data 2019-2023

Nearly 30% of personnel in the selected contract positions are found to be younger than 30 years, with an average duration of stay at CERN of nearly 4 years.

When applying these parameters to the estimated number of FCC-ee project participants (Section 3.1), it is found that roughly 30% of project participants would enjoy a training benefit. Consequently, 4 096 early career researchers were considered to benefit from a salary premium.

Table 38: Number of personnel under 30 who stay at the FCC-ee at CERN from 1 to 5 years by contract

PERSON DESCRIPTION	TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (ONLY CONSIDERING NEW ARRIVALS)	CUMULATED NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS OVER TIME
Estimated total number of people	14,202	258,107
Accelerator and Infrastructure	780	27,594
Experiment 1	4,737	81,463
Experiment 2	4,737	81,463
Experiments 3 + 4	3,948	67,588
Estimated number of people under 30 years old and between 1 and 5 years of service	4,096	74,448

Source: Authors. **Note:** The cumulated number of participants accounts for the total number of people who would be active on the project each year (the same individual can remain for more than one year).

➤ **STEP 2 - Determining the sector of work after leaving FCC-ee**

As a second step of this estimation, the Team determined the sector in which students and early-career researchers will be likely to work after the experience in the FCC-ee project. After discussions held with CERN (on November 28th, 2024 and on January 15th, 2025), the Team applied the following distribution:

- **36%** remain in the academia and research sector.
- **45%** move to the industry and finance sectors.
- **19%** move to the public administration sector and non-profit organisations.

This is the official distribution of where people engaged in CERN projects move when they leave CERN, which has been presented to the public and to invited visits (see this). It is based on a 2014 Alumni Survey. This distribution differs from the one used by [1]⁵² , which relies on data gathered from a more recent survey of 2,692 current and past members of the LHC and other experiments at CERN.

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimating the duration of the working life**

As the third step, the team estimated the duration of the active working period of individuals after their experience with the project. This duration represents the time during which people benefit from the salary premium under the assumption that the premium persists throughout their entire professional career. In line with and based on, the average active working life of individuals leaving the project—and, consequently, the number of years during which the salary premium is applied—is estimated to be **37.5 years**.

⁵² [1] assumed that 53% remain in the academia and research sector, 32% move to the industry and finance sectors, 15% move to the public administration sector and non-profit organisations. The uncertainty between the two surveys will be considered at a later stage in the Montecarlo simulation.

➤ **STEP 4 - Define the lifetime salary evolution for each different professional sector**

To monetize this benefit, the team used the salary functions estimated for each employment sector (industry, academia and public administration), as provided by. These salary functions were adjusted to 2024 prices using the GDP deflator. This adjustment resulted in an increase in salary progression across all three sectors as compared to the ones adopted by.

Figure 18 Lifetime salary of early-career researchers by sector of employment (CHF, 2024)

Source: Authors based on

➤ **STEP 5 - Estimate the average salary premium**

Similar to the approach used in [1], it was assumed that early-career researchers working on a project at CERN receive an average salary premium of 6%, with a range from 2% to 10%⁵³. This premium is applied over the average number of years they remain active in their professional careers after working on the project (37.5 years; see previous section for details).

Results

Using the parameters and data presented in previous sections, the total value of training benefits was estimated. Specifically, the estimated salary premium is applied to the salary functions by the professional sector and then multiplied by the estimated number of people students and early career researchers that would leave the FCC-ee project every year.

Overall, it was found that with an average salary premium of 6% (over an average duration of 37.5 years), the total benefit amounts to 20.7 billion CHF when considering undiscounted value and 4.9 CHF when considering discounted value. The training benefit extends well beyond the project's time

⁵³ Past studies provide evidence of the existence of this benefit [3, 4, 13, 14, 15]. For the LHC programme, the estimated premium ranges between 5% and 12% of the average salary, depending on the future professional sector, type of tasks carried out and skills acquired [14, 15].

horizon, as it persists throughout the entire working life of individuals, including those who leave the project in its final operational years. Because a substantial portion of these benefits occurs in the distant future, the discounting formula—which converts future benefits into present terms (as explained in Section 1.4)—has a significant impact on the total benefit value.

47% of this benefit is enjoyed by people who are likely to find a job in the industry, 32% in academia, and 21% in the public administration sector.

Figure 19 Total training benefits by professional sector – baseline scenario (CHF and %, undiscounted)

Source: Authors

The Figure below shows the time trend of the training benefit for early-career researchers who find a job either in the academic and research sector in industry and finance or in public administration and non-profit.

Figure 20 Time profile of training benefits by professional sector – baseline scenario (CHF, undiscounted).

Source: Authors. **Note:** Annual salary benefits generated for the three employment sectors considered (academia & research, industry & finance, public administration and non-profit). The x-axis shows the year in which the benefit is generated. The y-axis indicates the undiscounted amount of CHF generated in that year.

Different scenarios are derived by applying different salary premiums, ranging from a minimum of 2% (worst scenario) to a maximum of 10% (best scenario). The table below summarises the benefit (CHF, discounted value) obtained for each scenario and for each sector of employment. The Figure below shows the time profile of the total value calculated in the three scenarios.

Table 39: Total estimation – under different scenarios (CHF, 2024, discounted)

	Worst-case scenario	Baseline scenario	Best-case scenario
Academia and research	534,698,336	1,604,095,007	2,673,491,678
Industry and finance	777,849,774	2,333,549,322	3,889,248,871
Public administration and non-profit	349,611,763	1,048,835,290	1,748,058,816
TOTAL	1,662,159,873	4,986,479,619	8,310,799,365

Source: Authors **Note:** salary premium equal to 2% is considered in the best-case scenario, 6% in the baseline scenario, 2% in the worst-case scenario

Figure 21 Time profile of training benefits in the baseline, optimistic and pessimistic scenario (CHF, undiscounted).

Source: Authors. **Note:** Annual salary benefits generated for the three employment sectors considered (academia & research, industry & finance, public administration and non-profit). The x-axis shows the year in which the benefit is generated. The y-axis indicates the undiscounted amount of CHF generated in that year.

4.3. Industry: benefits for suppliers

Introduction

This benefit is related to the idea that the FCC-ee can be used by companies as a platform to bring their technologies to higher maturity or quality levels, to test out new developments, to find solutions to costly or time-intensive issues in an environment with low and controlled investment risks, which can eventually bring them additional market opportunities. Previous work on the LHC and the HL-LHC projects [see 3 and 8] found that the socio-economic benefits generated through procurement activities for the construction and operation of the research infrastructure, defined as procurement profit/sales multiplier (or economic utility/sales ratio), accounts for over one-third of all the project benefits. [16] empirically proved that CERN suppliers of highly innovative technologies for LHC benefited from higher profitability after their first contract with CERN. [17] demonstrated that becoming a supplier of CERN is associated with a statistically significant increase in the number of

patent applications by firms, even if this effect is observed in a relatively long-time range of five to eight years.

As explained in Box 1 (Executive Summary), the potential benefits arising from the establishment of spin-offs for the development of new technologies are excluded from this analysis because of uncertainties of their materialisation at this stage.

Estimation

In line with [1] and based on previous literature focusing on LEP [17,18], this benefit is estimated by looking at the incremental long-term benefits associated with direct supplier firms. This entailed the following steps:

➤ STEP 1 - Estimate the technological intensity level of FCC-ee investment

Taking into account the specific content and characteristics of the different FCC-ee systems listed in Section 2, CERN assigned two parameters to each investment cost item (as of 30 September 2024, at this [link](#)):

- A [fraction of the system concerned](#), which is the share of investment costs that can be considered leading to new or enhanced products and services, ranging from 0 to 1;
- A [technological intensity scale](#), indicating the degree of design work and knowledge creation intensity on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high). By following [16] – who classified a sample of 300 LHC orders - the following five-point scale was used:
 - 1) Very likely to be off-the-shelf products⁵⁴ with low technological intensity.
 - 2) Off-the-shelf products with an average technological intensity.
 - 3) Mostly off-the-shelf products, requiring limited design and engineering work according to detailed specifications.
 - 4) Products requiring project-related customisation and adaptation with a moderate to high design and engineering activity.
 - 5) Products requiring scratch developments and CERN/supplier co-developments or significant adaptation of an existing product or service for the project.

The specific attributions are presented in the Table below.

⁵⁴ Note that the term “product” also includes material treatments, consultancies, constructions, installations and other services.

Table 40: FCC-ee technological intensity levels and fractions of concerned project segments and subsystems.

SYSTEM	DOMAIN	FRACTION OF THE SYSTEM CONCERNED [0-1]	TECHNOLOGICAL INTENSITY SCALE [1-5]
Pre-investment studies	All	0.05	3
Collider magnets	Accelerator	0.5	5
Collider radiofrequency	Accelerator	0.5	5
Collider vacuum chambers	Accelerator	0.5	5
Power converters	Accelerator	0.3	3
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	0.3	3
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	0.2	3
Beam transfer elements	Accelerator	0.5	4
Beam intercepting devices	Accelerator	0.2	2
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	0.2	2
Beam instrumentation and diagnostics	Accelerator	0.8	5
Protection and interlock systems	Accelerator	0.5	4
Controls	Accelerator	0.3	3
Machine-Detector Interface	Accelerator	0.2	3
Machine-Detector Interface, 2 additional interaction points	Accelerator	0.2	3
Polarisation and energy calibration	Accelerator	0.2	3
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	0.5	5
Linear accelerator	Injector	0.5	5
Positron production	Injector	0.5	5
Damping ring and beam lines	Injector	0.5	5
Technical infrastructures	Injector	0.3	3
Transfer lines	Injector	0.5	4
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	0.4	3
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	0.4	3
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	0.5	3

Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	0.5	3
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	0.3	4
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	0.2	2
Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	0.2	2
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	0.3	3
Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	0.2	3
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	0.5	3
Subsurface civil engineering	Civil Engineering	0.4	3
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	Civil Engineering	0.3	3
Surface structures	Civil Engineering	0.4	3
Excavated materials management	Civil Engineering	0.3	5
CE planning, management, architecture, landscaping	Civil Engineering	0.4	3
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	0	1
20 kV connections	Territorial development	0	1
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	0.1	4
Access related costs	Territorial development	0	1
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	0	1
Administrative processes	Territorial development	0.5	4
Experiment 1	Experiment	0.7	4
Experiment 2	Experiment	0.7	4
Experiment 3	Experiment	0.7	4
Experiment 4	Experiment	0.7	4

Source: Authors based on CERN communication (as of September 30, 2024⁵⁵)

Multiplying the technological intensity capacity percentage by the assumed cost for each item (See Section 2), we obtain a distribution of investment costs by technological intensity level, as shown by the table below. The total value of investment items considered to have some technological intensity capacity amounts to 6.8 billion CHF, corresponding to 43% of the assumed total investment costs

⁵⁵ https://cernbox.cern.ch/files/spaces/eos/project/f/fccproject/fccis/WP4/socio_economic_analysis/complementary%20work%202024/costs/investment%20costs?items-per-page=100&view-mode=resource-table&tiles-size=1&sort-by=name&sort-dir=asc

(15.9 billion CHF). Of these investments, 46% have a moderate level of technological intensity, 20% have a high level, and 33% have a very high level of technological intensity.

Table 41: FCC-ee technological intensity levels and fractions of concerned project segments and subsystems.

Technological intensity capacity, relevant for industrial benefit generation	Million CHF (baseline scenario, undiscounted)	Share over total investment costs
2 - low (off-the-shelf products with an average technological and technological intensity)	67,200,000	1%
3 - moderate (mostly off-the-shelf products, usually high-tech and requiring detailed specifications)	3,136,400,000	46%
4 - high (high-tech and highly innovative products with a moderate to high specification activity intensity to customise a product for LHC)	1,341,600,000	20%
5 - very high (products at the frontier of technology with intensive customisation work and co-design involving CERN staff)	2,269,600,000	33%
Total value of FCC-ee investment items with technological capacity	6,814,800,000	100%

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 2 - Estimate the procurement profit/sales multiplier

Considering that the procurement multiplier derived for LHC procurement activities is very similar to the one previously estimated for LEP and recognizing that this multiplier does not significantly change over time, the same multiplier value was applied throughout the analysis for the FCC-ee project.

The industrial benefit of procurement was estimated as follows:

- Only the share of FCC-ee construction costs with a minimum level of technological intensity was considered.
- For investments with a high (level 4) or very high (level 5) technological intensity, a profit/sales multiplier of 3.06 was applied.
- For investments with low (level 2) or moderate (level 3) technological intensity, a multiplier value of 1.96 was used.
- A 5-year time lag was assumed between the contract start and the time when the first effects for the supplier materialize.

Since the industrial spillovers were calculated by applying the multiplier to the capital expenditure, the benefits for suppliers correlate linearly with the contract volumes.

Results

In the baseline scenario (i.e. assuming the average investment costs presented in Section 3.2.2), the benefit for industry suppliers amounts to 17.6 billion CHF (undiscounted) and 9.5 billion CHF (discounted). The Table below shows the benefit estimate if the minimum or the maximum investment costs are assumed, as from Table 4 presented in Section 2.

Table 42: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024)

	Baseline scenario [based on the average value of the investment costs]		Pessimistic scenario [based on the minimum value of the investment costs]		Optimistic scenario [based on the maximum value of the investment costs]	
	Total discounted (Million CHF)	Total undiscounted (Million CHF)	Total discounted (Million CHF)	Total undiscounted (Million CHF)	Total discounted (Million CHF)	Total undiscounted (Million CHF)
Total investment costs	10,171	16,215	9,555	15,264	12,080	19,312
Investment costs with high and very high innovation level	4,246	6,896	4,009	6,516	5,078	8,250
Industrial benefit for suppliers	9,569	17,577	9,029	16,595	11,441	21,024

Source: Authors

Figure 22 Time profile of FCC-ee industry benefits for suppliers, compared with the high-tech investment costs (CHF, undiscounted – baseline scenario)

Source: Authors

4.4. Cultural benefit

Engaging all citizens in science is one of the objectives of many research infrastructures. CERN is already managing and will continue to develop activities designed to attract the general public, such as exhibitions, open days, and guided tours. Additionally, social media, news articles, press releases, and websites serve as platforms for sharing research updates and insights. The Science Gateway⁵⁶, CERN’s visitor centre inaugurated in 2023, further reinforces CERN's commitment to increasing public

⁵⁶ <https://sciencegateway.cern/home>

engagement. The implementation of the FCC-ee is expected to boost the attractiveness of CERN and lead to an increase in the number of visitors.

To estimate the impacts of those "cultural benefits", we distinguish between benefits for onsite visitors and benefits for on-line ("virtual") visitors. They are discussed separately because the evaluation approaches are different.

4.4.1. On-site visitors

Introduction

On-site visitors to CERN are distinguished mainly in three categories:

- **CERN conventional visitors:** This category refers to persons that visit any or a combination of the CERN visit points, such as e.g. microcosm exhibition, the proton-synchrotron, the LEIR accelerator, the Antimatter Factory, the Synchrocyclotron, the Globe of Science and Innovation, the Science Gateway, the large magnet assembly facilities, S'Cool LAB and several other highlights.
- **Visitors to experiments:** these are part of a private group that visits the experiment only⁵⁷.
- **Open-day visitors:** these additional visitors are expected during open days which were assumed to occur every 5 to 7 years.

Adjustments from [1] were necessary to reflect new evidence gathered through a survey conducted between November 2023 and December 2024 (hereafter CERN survey to visitors). Specifically, for the purpose of estimating this benefit, survey data extracted by CERN on December 16th, 2024, were used. This dataset included 3,547 responses collected since November 2023. The team, in collaboration with CERN, performed data cleaning activities to remove frivolous and inconsistent responses, thereby enhancing the overall quality of the replies. Ultimately, 3,086 responses were used (see the next section for details).

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Estimating the number of FCC-ee-related visitors

To estimate the socio-economic cultural impacts for onsite visitors, first, the number of visitors that are expected to visit CERN because of the FCC has to be estimated.

Currently, CERN welcomes over 400,000 visitors per year, confirming that the projections made by [1] for a scenario with FCC-ee have already materialised. According to a CERN survey of visitors, 24% of visitors come as part of groups, while 76% are individual visitors. Based on CERN's survey of tourists, 55% are classified as "CERN motivated" visitors, whose primary purpose of the trip was to visit CERN, while 45% are "Region motivated" visitors, who travelled to the area for other reasons and took the chance to also visit CERN.

⁵⁷ According to information provided by CERN (as of January 15th, 2025), these visitors are not included in the total visitor count, as they participate in private guided tours.

Table 43 Respondents by visitor type and rationale of visits

MOTIVATION	INDIVIDUAL VISITORS	GROUP	TOTAL
CERN motivated	1,164	540	1,704
Region motivated	1,173	209	1,382
Total	2,337	749	3,086

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey of tourists

According to estimates provided by CERN (as of January 31st, 2024), a total of 19 million visitors are expected to be welcomed in a scenario with FCC-ee over the period 2024–2064 (see the table below for details). The expected trend of these visitors is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 23 Number of visitors forecasted in the FCC-ee project scenario

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of January 31st, 2025)

Based on survey results and in agreement with CERN (as of January 15th, 2025), it was assumed that only a portion of the projected visitors would visit CERN specifically because of FCC-ee. For this reason, the following assumptions were applied:

- **Conventional CERN visits:** an increasing share of these visitors is attributed to FCC-ee, starting at 0% in 2024 and gradually rising to 50% by 2064.
- **Visitors to the FCC-ee construction sites and the four experimental sites:** these visitors are fully attributed to FCC-ee, as they would not have been accounted for in a scenario without FCC-ee.
- **Visits to the decommissioned LHC tunnel:** adhering to a conservative approach, these are not attributed to FCC-ee since they would be justified even in the absence of the FCC-ee.
- **Open-day visitors:** these are attributed to FCC-ee only for the additional capacity created by the new accelerator; all other visitors are excluded from the count.

Based on these assumptions, it is estimated that out of 19.9 million visitors, 5.5 million will be attracted by FCC-ee, while the remaining will be motivated more by the overall CERN activity and longstanding reputation of world scientific excellence. Details of these estimations, broken down by visitor type and the expected trend over the period, are provided in the table and figure below. As the next steps, the team will fine-tune these assumptions to assess their suitability and revise them as necessary. Any residual uncertainty will be addressed through Monte Carlo simulations.

Table 44: Number of expected CERN visitors, 2024-2064

SITE	VISITOR TYPE	N OF VISITORS WITH FCC-EE	N OF VISITORS WITH FCC-EE, ATTRIBUTABLE TO FCC-EE
Open Day Visits	Individual	680,000	230,000
	Group	0	0
Conventional CERN visits (it includes the Science Gateway)	Individual	10,475,000	1,149,750
	Group	3,874,500	425,250
Construction site visits to 6 sites: PA, PD, PF, PG, PJ, PL (no individual visits are possible)	Individual	0	0
	Group	960,000	960,000
No longer operated LHC and LHC Experiment sites (no individual visits are possible)	Individual	0	0
	Group	672,000	0
FCC-ee experiments and visitor centres	Individual	1,272,000	1,272,000
	Group	1,536,000	1,536,000
Sub-Total	Individual	11,977,500	2,651,750
	Group	7,042,500	2,921,250
Total		19,020,000	5,573,000

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of January 31st, 2025)

Figure 24: Number of on-site visitors attracted by FCC-ee over the period 2024-2064

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication (as of January 31st, 2025)

➤ **STEP 2 - Estimating the willingness to pay of onsite visitors**

In line with previous studies [1, 3, 8], the cultural benefit for onsite visitors is valued by estimating the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for a visit through the travel cost method. According to this method, costs incurred to reach the destination and experience the visit are a good measure of the socio-economic value of reaching and visiting CERN/FCC-ee. Along this line, the socio-economic value per visitor is estimated as the sum of:

- the cost incurred by visitors to travel to CERN and the FCC;
- the value of time spent travelling;
- the expenditures connected to their visit

As to the first component of the travel cost method formula, the travel cost depends on the distance, i.e. the country of origin of the visitor and the transport mode used (plane, train, bus/car). On the basis of information on the origin country of visitors provided by the CERN survey of tourists, it was possible to calculate the share of visitors by distance and type of visitors (individuals or in group), and, for each combination (type of visitor and distance), the share of visitors by transport mode, being it either a car/bus, train or plane (see Table below). The larger share of visitors originates from a distance ranging from 500km to 1500km, while the second most popular group is comprised of local visitors. As for the means of transport, plane is the only viable choice for long-distance trips, while the composition remains much more heterogeneous for short distances. Cars are the most popular means (81% for groups and 66% for individuals) for the 50-500km range category.

Table 45 Share of visitors by distance and transport mode

	SHARE OF VISITORS	DISTANCE (MIDPOINT KM)	ROUNDRIP (KM)	CAR/BUS/ TRAM	TRAIN	PLANE	TOTAL
Group visitors							
less than 50 km	30%	40	80	56%	39%	5%	100%
50 - 500 km	8%	300	600	81%	8%	11%	100%
501 - 1500 km	45%	1000	2000	40%	3%	57%	100%
> 1500 km	16%	2000	4000	0%	1%	99%	100%
Total	100%						
Individual visitors							
less than 50 km	30%	40	80	65%	30%	5%	100%
50 - 500 km	9%	300	600	66%	13%	21%	100%
501 - 1500 km	36%	1000	2000	43%	12%	45%	100%
> 1500 km	26%	2000	4000	0%	0%	99%	100%
Total	100%						

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

The average travel cost by distance, transport mode and type of visitors was then estimated (see Table below). It is generally higher for individuals because, according to the survey responses, they typically prefer travelling by plane, while group visitors, which include many school trips, tend to come from closer locations, e.g. Switzerland, France).

Table 46 Average travel cost by distance and type of visitor (CHF 2024)

DISTANCE	CERN MOTIVATED GROUP VISITOR	REGION MOTIVATED GROUP VISITOR	OF WHICH ATTRIBUTABLE TO CERN	CERN MOTIVATED INDIVIDUAL VISITOR	REGION MOTIVATED INDIVIDUAL VISITOR	OF WHICH ATTRIBUTABLE TO CERN
less than 50 km	102.56	174.64		106.76	195.59	
50 - 500 km	155.19	215.70	81.30	234.24	272.92	83.70
501 - 1500 km	324.82	303.12		246.53	307.93	
> 1500 km	468.95	505.74		535.53	527.36	
TOTAL	264.04	325.21		289.62	334.81	

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

As to the second component of the travel cost method formula, the value of travel time reflects the opportunity cost of time measured by the amount of hourly salary that the visitor forgoes while travelling. It directly depends on the distance and the transport mode. The following assumptions were applied:

- The number of hours needed for a roundtrip for each mode of transport was estimated as a weighted average between the hours travelled and the share of visitors by specific transport mode
- For travel by car/bus, it is taken a speed of 70 km/h on average;
- For travels by train, it is taken an average speed of 70 km/h;
- For travels by plane, the time to reach the airport and the time before boarding is considered, in addition to the average duration of a flight roundtrip.

The value of travel time per hour was taken from [1] and adjusted to 2024 prices. A baseline salary of 15.4 CHF 2024 (with 8 and 20.4 hourly salaries as the pessimistic and optimistic reference values)

Table 47: Value of travel time per hour (CHF/hour).

SCENARIO	CHF/HOUR, 2024	PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION
Pessimistic scenario	8	35%
Baseline scenario	15.4	50%
Optimistic scenario	20.4	15%

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

By multiplying the share of visitors by distance, the number of hours travelled (see table below), and the value of travel time by distance, we obtained the average value of travel time by distance for both individual and group visitors

Table 48: Average travel time (roundtrip) by distance and transport mode – Hours

DISTANCE	MID -POINT (KM)	ROUNDRIP (KM)	CAR/BUS (HOURS)	TRAIN (HOURS)	PLANE (HOURS)	TOTAL TIME (HOURS) - WEIGHTED AVG
CERN visitors in group (N= 540)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.19
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.98
501 - 1500 km	1000	2000	28.6	28.6	4	13.55
> 1500 km	2000	4000	57.1	57.1	8	8.72
Region visitors in group (N= 209)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.17
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.53
501 - 1500 km	1000	2000	28.6	28.6	4	17.49
> 1500 km	2000	4000	57.1	57.1	8	8.00
CERN Individual visitors (N= 1,164)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.17
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.36
501 - 1500 km	1000	2000	28.6	28.6	4	19.83
> 1500 km	2000	4000	57.1	57.1	8	8.21
Region Individual visitors (N= 1,173)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.19
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.31
501 - 1500 km	1000	2000	28.6	28.6	4	17.60
> 1500 km	2000	4000	57.1	57.1	8	8.43

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

For the third component of the travel cost method, the team considered onsite expenditures, including accommodation costs, food and drink expenses, and souvenirs.

In order to properly account for FCC-ee attribution, a distinct willingness to pay (WTP) was calculated for CERN-motivated and region-motivated visitors. According to the results of the CERN survey of tourists, CERN-motivated visitors stay in the area for three days, while region-motivated visitors tend to stay longer, around four days, to visit other attractions in the region. For the purpose of WTP estimation, the following assumptions were made:

- For CERN-motivated visitors, the willingness to pay corresponds to 100% of the value of travel time, travel costs, and local expenses.

- For region-motivated visitors the willingness to pay is calculated on the assumption that they spend one day at CERN. For this reason, only 25% of the value of travel time and travel costs is attributed to FCC-ee, while local expenses are considered for just one day.

Detailed figures of onsite expenditure by item, distinguishing between CERN-motivated and region-motivated visitors (individual versus group), are provided in the table below. The daily average local expenditure of visitors incurred for a visit in the region is between 180 CHF for visitors in groups to 185 CHF for individual visitors. For CERN-motivated visitors, that figure is multiplied by the duration of the visit (3 days on average). Therefore, they total local expenditure amounts to 539 for groups and to 554 for individuals.

Table 49: Average expenditure for each visitor by item (CHF, baseline scenario).

	CERN visitors in group (n= 540)	Region visitors in group (n= 209)	CERN individual visitors (n= 1,164)	Region individual visitors (n= 1,173)
Accommodation	236	79	328	109
Food and drinks	160	53	68	23
Souvenirs	94	31	91	30
Visits to other sites (museums, exhibitions), excl. CERN	49	16	68	23
Subtotal local expenditure	<i>(49%)</i> 539	<i>(52%)</i> 180	<i>(49%)</i> 554	<i>(57%)</i> 185
Travel cost	<i>(24%)</i> 264	<i>(23%)</i> 81	<i>(25%)</i> 290	<i>(26%)</i> 84
Value of time	<i>(27%)</i> 297	<i>(86%)</i> 86	<i>(26%)</i> 299	<i>(17%)</i> 53
TOTAL	<i>(100%)</i> 1,100	<i>(100%)</i> 347	<i>(100%)</i> 1,143	<i>(100%)</i> 322

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

When considering the full travel cost, i.e. the sum of local expenditure, travel cost and the value of travel time, the total expenditure is between 347 and 1 143 CHF. The average expenditure for each day depends on the motivation and is around 757 CHF per CERN-motivated visitor and 335 per region motivated visitor.

Figure 25: Share of expenditure for onsite CERN-motivated visitors in groups and individuals (2023-2024).

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

As shown in the table below, CERN-motivated individuals and groups have a higher WTP compared to Region-motivated visitors.

Table 50 WTP of CERN visitors in the baseline scenario, CHF 2024

MOTIVATION		INDIVIDUAL VISITORS		GROUP	
		Total WTP per person	Of which local expenses	Total WTP per person	Of which local expenses
(CERN motivated)	Total	1,143	554	1,100	539
	Daily*	/	185	/	180
Region motivated	Total	322	185	347	180
	Daily*	/	185	/	180

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to tourists

*The value of time and the travel cost do not change according to the number of days

Results

To estimate the total cultural benefit for onsite visitors, the number of visitors attributable to the FCC-ee – distinguishing between individuals and groups - is multiplied by their respective WTP. The discounted benefit generated by onsite visitors is estimated to be approximately 2.1 billion CHF in the baseline scenario (see Table below). Using the minimum and maximum values of time presented above, the worst-case and best-case scenarios are also calculated. The time profile of this benefit is shown in the Figure below. As a next step, additional variation could be tested by adjusting the visitors' attribution percentages to FCC.

Figure 26. Time profile of the cultural benefit for onsite visitors (CHF, undiscounted).

Table 51: Total estimation under different scenarios (CHF, 2024)

	Total discounted	Total undiscounted
Worst case scenario	1,873,955,235	3,998,949,149
Baseline scenario	2,129,401,261	4,538,092,491
Best case scenario	2,328,826,096	4,967,273,447

Source: Authors

4.4.2. Online visitors

Introduction

This benefit relates to the value accrued by virtual visitors engaging in a wide range of activities, from consulting textual information to watching videos and interacting with social media. Similarly to [1], the impacts from the following on-line channels are considered:

- Visits to social media accounts are managed by CERN, including two types of activities: impressions (number of times a piece of content is seen) and engagements (number of actions, such as likes or shares, taken on a piece of content). Specifically, the following types of social networks are considered in the analysis:
 - Personal network (e.g. Facebook)
 - Photos network (e.g. Instagram)
 - Text/short information network (e.g. Twitter)
 - Professional network (e.g. LinkedIn)
 - Video network (e.g. Youtube).
- Visits to the CERN-managed websites
 - CERN main website
 - Websites of the LHC experiment collaborations.

Due to data availability constraints, the analysis focuses on virtual visits to the content directly managed by the CERN. For this reason, the figures presented must be considered as a lower-bound estimate of on-line cultural benefits today. In particular, the estimation does not include:

- On-line visits to social media content produced by the experiments (i.e., through their own accounts and pages);
- Participants in the virtual tours that CERN started organising during the COVID-19 period;

Cultural benefits derived from exposure to CERN or FCC-related content produced by other media (e.g., newspapers, websites, forums, blogs, or social media pages not managed by CERN) represent an "online echo" from FCC activities. While these benefits are related to the project, they cannot be entirely attributed to it, as they are more of an indirect benefit. For this reason, they are not accounted for here.

Estimation

The benefit estimate is carried out in two sequential steps: the estimation of the volume of on-line visits expected to be directly caused by the FCC project and the economic valuation of the time spent during these visits.

➤ STEP 1 – Estimating the volume of on-line visits

The number of online visitors estimated by [1] is based on historical data collected by CERN's communication group regarding visits to the main CERN website and social media accounts. Assumptions were made about the number of visits specifically related to FCC-ee. This estimate has been revised to reflect changes in the project's timeline and to ensure consistency with the revisions made in the estimation of onsite visitors, particularly regarding the share of FCC-ee attribution. It is

now assumed that the highest attributable share of visits is approximately 50%, aligning with the assumption made for the total CERN visitors (as discussed in the previous section).

In the scenario without the FCC, it is assumed that the number of on-line visits to websites and social media will follow the same patterns as the on-site visitors in the absence of the FCC-ee. In the scenario with the FCC, the number of on-line visits corresponds to the trend of growth of the scientific publications due to the FCC-ee. The share of online visits attributable to the FCC-ee starts as a marginal share of the total CERN on-line visits. The main jump in on-line visits is expected to occur in 2048, with the start of operations. Then, this share is expected to grow further during the operative phase. The number of on-line visitors is expected to reach its maximum between 2051 and 2064. In these years, the share of the total CERN on-line visits associated with the FCC reaches about 50% in 2051 and remains constant after that.

Figure 27 Share of total CERN on-line visits associated with the FCC-ee

Source: Authors

These revised growth patterns have been applied to historical data on CERN's online traffic, as provided by the CERN communications group. Future growth trends are assumed to be consistent across all types of social media, as well as for both engagements and impressions. Due to the adjustments made in this analysis—affecting both on-site visitors and publications—the estimated number of attributable impressions, engagements, and online visitors has been revised accordingly. Specifically, for the FCC-ee over the 2024–2064 period, impressions are estimated at 1.7 billion, engagements at 79 million, and CERN website visits at 175 million.

The time profile of impressions, engagements and visits to the CERN website is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 28 Estimates of impressions related to FCC-ee on CERN-managed social media (incremental scenario)

Source: Authors

Figure 29 Estimates of engagements related to FCC-ee on CERN-managed social media (incremental scenario).

Source: Authors

Figure 30 Estimates of visits to the CERN website

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 2 – Estimating the average time spent for each visitor**

Building on [1], the amount of time spent for the visits to social media was assumed as follows:

Table 52 Average time spent by social media and type of visit

Social media	Time spent on an impression	Time spent on an engagement
Personal network	4 second	1 second
Photos network	3 second	1 second
Text/short information sharing	4 second	1 second
Professional network	4 second	1 second
Video network	246 second	1 second

Source: Authors processing of [1]

As for the website, in line with [1], a visit is assumed to last on average 203.49 seconds (a bit more than 3 minutes)

By multiplying the number of visits generated by the FCC-ee by the estimated time per visit, the total time spent by virtual visitors on CERN social media is calculated. Based on the times indicated in the table above, it is estimated that approximately 17 billion seconds, or 203,000 days, will be spent on social media during the 2024–2064 period due to the FCC-ee.

Time spent on impressions is significantly higher than on engagements, as impressions account for 99.5% of the total. Videos contribute the largest share, with approximately 11 billion seconds (or around 130,000 days) spent watching video content. This is attributed to the longer duration of videos compared to other content types. Personal networks (e.g., Facebook) and text/short information networks (e.g., Twitter) are also key contributors, making up 13% and 12% of the total time spent, respectively.

Since the average time per visit is assumed to remain constant throughout the observation period, the total time spent reflects the evolution of visit volumes.

➤ **STEP 3 – Estimating the marginal social value of time**

In line with [1], the value of time spent is determined using the "opportunity cost" method, which suggests that time spent on social media and websites represents a missed opportunity to engage in other potentially profitable activities. Since not all virtual visitors are necessarily part of the economically active workforce, the opportunity cost of time was estimated by using per capita GDP (instead of wages), adjusted based on the geographical distribution of virtual visitors.

Building on the value adopted by [1] and underlying assumptions on the country of origin of visitors, as well as the correspondence between GDP and time⁵⁸, the following values are calculated for each type of interaction:

⁵⁸ [1] assumes that GDP corresponds to the output produced for 365.25 days, each one composed of 24 hours of 3 600 seconds, The value of a second of time for a visitor was calculated by dividing the yearly GDP per capita by 31.5 million seconds in a year.

Table 53: Monetary valuation by type of visits in 2021

SOCIAL MEDIA	MONETARY VALUE OF EACH IMPRESSION OR VISIT IN 2024 (CHF 2024)	MONETARY VALUE OF EACH ENGAGEMENT IN 2024 (CHF 2024)
Personal network	0.0074	0.0018
Photos network	0.0055	0.0018
Text/short information sharing	0.0074	0.0018
Professional network	0.0074	0.0018
Video network	0.4545	0.0018
CERN websites	0.3764	Not applicable

Source: Authors processing of [1] Note: prices adopted by [1] have been expressed in 2024 values.

Results

The total undiscounted cultural benefit for on-line visitors is estimated to be approximately 102 million CHF (undiscounted). Visits to the CERN social media account for 32% of the benefits over the entire period, compared to 68% for the visits to the websites.

Table 54: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024).

	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED	TOTAL DISCOUNTED
CERN social media	73,569,596	32,797,160
CERN websites	155,623,008	69,376,386
Total online cultural benefits	229,192,604	102,173,545

Source: Authors

4.5. IT innovations

Benefits from the development of detector simulation software and other advancements

Introduction

Evidence collected for this analysis suggests that the FCC-ee is likely to contribute to the development of a successor to the existing digital repository (e.g., Zenodo-like) or a web collaboration platform (e.g., Indico-like). However, market and technological evolution in the IT field within the business sector and in other scientific fields, such as astrophysics and biology is extremely fast and may generate a range of platforms. The precise attribution to the FCC-ee of any updates or new platforms at this stage would not be conservative. As a result, the value of such developments has been excluded from the quantitative analysis.

It is confirmed, however, that the FCC-ee will require new simulation software for the detectors and data analysis, with unique challenges to be dealt with. Currently Geant4 is one of the several software packages available as open-source software from CERN, which has been developed in relation to LHC needs. It is likely that the construction of a new circular collider, such as the FCC-ee, will generate the need to significantly innovate the detector simulation software and replace or significantly enhance the currently existing Geant4. Like Geant4, the new software can find use in the non-HEP community, thereby generating a spillover benefit for society. A number of further innovations can be related to the usage of artificial intelligence in this area or the introduction of quantum sensing and computing. Some of these developments are unpredictable, but it is clear that the collaborations around the FCC-ee experiments will be able to make significant contributions to simulation software development.

In line with [1], the benefit generated by the development of an upgraded detector simulation software is estimated by following the approach suggested by [3].

Estimation

This estimation followed the approach outlined by [1], with the adjustment of values to CHF 2024. Specifically, it was based on the following steps.

➤ STEP 1 – Estimation of the user community outside CERN

As a first step of this estimation, the team calculated the number of institutes and companies (not individual users) potentially using simulation software.

For Geant4, [3] identified approximately 50 research centres, space agencies, and companies using the software. This included 38 institutions that contributed in some way to its development (excluding CERN), such as Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory, SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, the Centre for Medical Radiation Physics, and the European Space Agency. Additionally, 12 other laboratories, institutes, and companies utilized the Geant4 license without contributing to its development, including NASA, General Electric, Philips, Siemens, Varian, Boeing, and General Motors. These figures are not updated and reflect the user community as of 2006⁵⁹. CERN unfortunately does not keep track of the number of users and installations. However, some more updated data⁶⁰ suggest a current user community of about 95 contributing institutes as of 2023, excluding CERN, comprising members of the Geant4 collaboration or external contributors. Assuming the 2006 ratio of 3:1 between contributing and non-contributing institutions remains consistent, the total number of non-contributing users is estimated to be around 30. In the absence of more reliable data, this estimate is considered reasonable and conservative.

➤ STEP 2 – Estimation of the avoided costs

The benefit is estimated as the avoided cost for the external users, and it is based on the production cost of new software.

It was estimated that the production cost of Geant4 was about 44.2 million CHF up to 2013⁶¹, covering the first 20 years of its development starting in 1994, amounted to approximately 44.2 million CHF. This estimate was based on the effort required to develop the 2 million lines of C++ code and an average annual salary of around 56,000 USD for those involved. [3] assumed that CERN contributed

59 <http://Geant4.web.cern.ch/Geant4/license/>

60 <https://Geant4.web.cern.ch/collaboration/members>

61 Expressed in 2024 CHF terms.

50% of this cost (22 million CHF), with the remaining amount funded by other external contributors. Using the same cost figures for the FCC-ee software and assuming CERN's contribution remains at 50%, the average contribution to the production cost for each laboratory is calculated to be 232,591 CHF (50% of 44.2 million CHF divided by 95). The avoided cost for each contributing laboratory is the total estimated production cost minus their specific contribution, while the avoided cost for non-contributing users is the full production cost. The table below shows that the benefit difference between a contributor and a non-contributor is minimal, while the benefit for a contributor in relation to their engagement is substantial. This estimate, on the side, is not considering, however, possible cost-sharing arrangements in a counterfactual scenario. On the other side, the multiplicative effects of imitation in a highly dynamic digital ecosystem are also not considered. Thus it is assumed that these unknown effects might be of the same size and cancel out. Risk analysis will be developed at a later stage.

Table 55: Production cost of a Geant4-like detector design and/or simulation software

DESCRIPTION OF COST ELEMENT	TOTAL PRODUCTION COST OF GEANT4 BETWEEN 1994 AND 2013 (CHF, 2024)	AVERAGE YEARLY PRODUCTION COST OF GEANT4 (CHF, 2024)
A - Total cost (including markup and code) for the software development	44,192,341	2,209,617
B - Production cost born by CERN (A*50%)	22,096,171	1,104,809
C - Production cost born by other contributing institutes (A-B)	22,096,171	1,104,809
	Total development cost of the new FCC-ee simulation software in the first 20 years (CHF)	Average yearly production cost of the new FCC-ee simulation software
D - Total cost (including markup and code) for the new software development (D=A)	44,192,341	2,209,617
E - Development cost born by each external contributor (non-CERN) (C/95)	232,591	11,630
F - Avoided cost for each contributing institute (F=D-E)	43,959,750	2,197,988
G - Avoided costs for each other non-contributing institute (G=D)	44,192,341	2,209,617

Source: Authors

It is assumed that new software would be developed starting from 2031 but further developments will continue even during the FCC-ee operation. For comparison, the first version of Geant4 available to external users was released in 1999, after 5 years of development, but its update continued in the following years. Version 11 was released in December 2022. The production cost paid by the contributing labs is assumed to be distributed uniformly starting from 2031 to 2064 (the year of the last infrastructure upgrade)

Results

The total cumulated avoided cost representing the total undiscounted benefit is estimated to be 7 428 million CHF. The discounted benefit is 4 375 million CHF at the 2.8% social discount rate. This benefit, in fact, would stand for a range of potential software developments that cannot be explored in detail at this stage.

Table 56: Total estimation – under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

BENEFIT DESCRIPTION	TOTAL DISCOUNTED (MILLION)	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED (MILLION)
Simulation software development - contributing labs	3 321	5 638
Simulation software development - non-contributing labs	1 054	1 790
Simulation software development	4 375	7 428

Source: Authors

5. ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

5.1. Provision of excess capacity clean electricity to society

Introduction

The FCC study commissioned a feasibility analysis for the supply of electricity from RES to two companies who regularly carry out such investigations, McKinsey and Accenture. According to the results of such studies, the FCC and the CERN can be supplied with RES during operation at a stable cost thanks to the use of multiple incremental long-term power purchasing agreements (PPAs). These agreements will provide planning security for electricity suppliers that lets them invest in building up significant RES capacities in the GW range for which only a part would be used for the FCC because the particle collider is characterised by a varying operation pattern throughout the year and over its fifteen years of operation. The unused capacities can be made available for other users, thus helping to speed up the energy transition and access to RES at a competitive cost. Including in a PPA the condition to make excess energy available to the market would lead to the generation of a societal impact by supplying electricity from RES to society. This will also allow avoiding CO₂eq by producing electricity with the new power plants, instead of the current energy mix.

The above-mentioned studies advise to conclude a set of long-term off-site baseload physical PPAs (see Box below). Specifically, it is estimated that concluding a set of long-term off-site baseload physical wind power PPAs would permit covering more than 60% of CERN's electricity need for the FCC period. Offshore wind has been identified as a key technology for CERN for power supply, to be procured "investment-alike" manner via PPAs that support the development of a new offshore wind park located in France, with a partner who makes the capital investment and carry the construction and operational risks. Adding a solar energy component would permit covering 80% of CERN's electricity need for the FCC period with excess capacity that can be made available to the market.

Box 4: PPA types

Off-site PPA is a contract associated with a utility-scale plant connected to the transmission or distribution network of the country's electricity system to take energy from its point of origin to the consumer point. Off-site PPAs can be further distinguished depending on the delivery point (physical, virtual, sleeved) or how the energy is delivered (as produced, baseload, and consumed). Based on the first categorization, a physical PPA is a contract where the renewable developer sells the renewable energy to an end consumer either directly or through an energy retailer, which supplies the energy from the renewable asset. Missing energy is supplied from the retailer's generation portfolio. At the end of the month, the consumer receives a single bill for all its consumption, whether from the dedicated RE installation under the PPA or other resources of the developer under the PPA or at the sports market.

Based on the second categorization, the baseload PPA is a contract where the renewable developers convert the gross generation from the plant into a duration-based pre-defined volume (e.g. yearly) called baseload. The consumer agrees to buy a total volume of energy over a period spanning typically several years. Profile and volume risks are with the seller, who may be the developer or an intermediary entity. If the seller cannot meet its obligations through its plants, the agreed volume will be sourced from the spot market.

Source: Authors based on Renewable Energy Supply Feasibility Analysis

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying CERN energy needs

The total energy needs for CERN and FCC-ee have been estimated for the 15 years of FCC-ee operation, as shown in Table 57. In total, CERN will use 28.5 TWh of energy, 22.25 TWh of which will be used by FCC-ee only, corresponding to a share that goes from 55% (in the year when FCC-ee is shut down for upgrades) to 77% in the last years of operation at maximum energy capacity.

For the purpose of this analysis, it is assumed that, in the baseline scenario, CERN and the FCC-ee will be supplied with 80% of their electricity needed from a mix of renewable sources (specifically, 60% from offshore wind and 20% from solar PV). In the best-case scenario, this percentage would increase to 95%, while in the worst-case scenario, it would decrease to 60% (only offshore wind).

Since the particle collider is characterised by a varying operation pattern throughout the year and over its fifteen years of operation, CERN will be able to make a portion of its originally contracted offshore wind capacity from PPAs available to society. Moreover, since renewables are not available all the time, it will need to buy some additional energy from the market. The grid would still be necessary for some hours when CERN's demand is higher than the contracted renewable power production.

Table 57: Amount of energy used for CERN or FCC-ee only, either sold to the market or bought from the market (baseline scenario).

	TOTAL ENERGY USED BY CERN (TWH)	ENERGY FRACTION USED BY FCC-EE (%)	TOTAL ENERGY USED FOR FCC-EE (TWH)	ENERGY BOUGHT FROM PPA FOR FCC-EE (TWH)	ENERGY BOUGHT FROM THE MARKET FOR FCC-EE (TWH)	ENERGY SOLD TO THE MARKET BY FCC-EE (TWH)
Z pole year 1	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 2	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 3	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 4	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
WW year 1	1.90	68%	1.3	1.0	0.3	0.7
WW year 2	1.90	68%	1.3	1.0	0.3	0.7
HZ year 1	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
HZ year 2	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
HZ year 3	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
Upgrade (1y)	1.01	55%	0.55	0.4	0.1	0.3
Top year 1	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 2	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 3	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 4	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 5	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Sub-total	28.55	-	20.90	16.72	4.18	12.14
Other phases*	Na	-	1,80	1.40	0.35	Na
Total	Na	-	22.65	18.12	4.53	Na

* Transition phase (2046 and 2027) and analysis phase (2063 and 2064)

Source: Authors based on McKinsey study but re-scaled to match the latest data on electricity consumption made available by CERN.

In the baseline scenario, the baseload of offshore wind production available to society would amount to approximately 1.4 TWh per year (see table below). The assumption is that this additional offshore wind production capacity will become available to society earlier than it would in the absence of CERN PPAs for the FCC-ee project. However, this benefit is limited to five years (from 2046 to 2050), as the energy mix is anyway expected to evolve by 2050 to meet the climate neutrality objective.

Table 58: Baseload for CERN or FCC-ee and for the society (baseline scenario).

	UNIT	VALUE
Baseload for CERN per year	%	60%
Baseload for the society per year	%	40%
Baseload for CERN per year	TWh	2.1
Baseload for the society per year	TWh	1.4

Source: Authors based on material received from CERN

In the worst-case scenario, the baseload values remain the same as in the baseline because the expected shares of offshore wind used by CERN and made available to society do not change. In the best-case scenario, the share of offshore wind used by CERN increases (from 60% to 75%), reducing the baseload available to society.

The fact that society will have access to excess offshore wind capacity from CERN will also help avoid CO2eq emissions by producing electricity with the new power plants rather than relying on the current energy mix. To quantify the emissions saved, the following GHG intensity factors were used:

Table 59: CO2eq intensity factors.

	VALUE (G CO2EQ/KWH)	SOURCE
GHG intensity of electricity generation (EU27)	203	European Environment Agency
GHG intensity of electricity generation (France)	58,0	Ademe Base Carbone (and annual decrease of 4% used for the calculation of CO2)
GHG emissions estimates for offshore wind power (France)	15.6	Ademe Base Carbone

Source: Authors based on cited sources

➤ **STEP 2 – Monetisation**

The socio-economic value of the energy produced and made available to society can be valued using the **Levelized Cost of Electricity** (LCOE), which is a commonly used metric that calculates the average cost of generating one unit of electricity over the lifetime of a generation asset, accounting for capital, operation, maintenance, and fuel costs.⁶² It is expressed in terms of cost per unit of energy produced (e.g., EUR/MWh). Although LCOE is a well-developed and standard technique in evaluating energy sector economics, authors (see box on different sources for LCOE) approach model formulation in various ways, leading to significant variations in the reported figures.

Box 5: LCOE sources

There are many organisations that estimate LCOE values on an annual basis; a few of them are:

- BNEF analyses LCOE for the different power generation technologies
- Lazard determines the LCOE of all technologies in the power sector of the USA
- IRENA estimates the renewable power generation costs across the world on a periodic basis.
- IEA, as part of its annual flagship report, World Energy Outlook (WEO), has long-term projections of LCOE up to 2050 for the different power generation technologies.

⁶² The LCOE does not take into account the specific territorial conditions of electricity production: in particular the significant French state subsidies to offshore wind farms. The result of the benefit is therefore overestimated.

Furthermore, various government organisations have developed LCOE models customised for their respective countries, such as the US LCOE model by the Department of Energy (DOE)⁶³ and the UK Government’s electricity costs model developed by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), amongst many others.

In France, RTE⁶⁴ recently studied the evolution of average costs for future renewable energy installations in the country.

Source: Authors

For the purpose of this study, the LCOE values from the RTE study⁶⁵ were primarily considered and supplemented with values from the International Energy Agency (IEA) and a European Commission study⁶⁶. The following table summarises the values.

Table 60: LCOE values

TECHNOLOGY	SHARE IN THE TOTAL FRENCH ENERGY PRODUCTION	LCOE (EUR/MWH)
Offshore wind	0.5%	40*
Onshore wind	9.8%	40*
Solar photovoltaic	4.4%	30*
Nuclear	64.8%	65*
Thermique fossile	6.6%	100
Thermique renouvelable et déchets	6.6%	100
Hydraulique	11.9%	100
France electricity mix		68

Note: * Average values from RTE (2022) Futurs énergétiques 2050.

Source: Authors

For the CO2 savings, the most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO2eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal [see 7].⁶⁷ One ton of CO2eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

⁶³ NREL (<https://www.nrel.gov/>) is a national laboratory of the U.S. Department of Energy. Among other things, it provides an online Levelized Cost of Energy Calculator: <https://www.nrel.gov/analysis/tech-lcoe.html>.

⁶⁴ See [32] in Reference section.

⁶⁵ Ibidem.

⁶⁶ See [33] in Reference section.

⁶⁷ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see [39] in Reference section.

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO₂eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

The first part of the benefit is calculated by multiplying the amount of electricity supplied by CERN to the market by the difference between the estimated LCOE of the French grid electricity mix and the LCOE of the electricity provided by CERN. The second part of the benefit is calculated by multiplying the value of a ton of CO₂eq by the difference between the estimated CO₂eq emissions associated with the grid electricity mix and the CO₂eq emission associated with the offshore wind baseload electricity made available by CERN to society. This benefit would span from 2046 to 2050, i.e. the 5 years of operation until 2050.

In the baseline scenario, the total undiscounted benefit for society is 227.1 million CHF. The discounted value is 117.3 million CHF. The largest portion of this benefit (85%) arises from the first component, i.e. the availability of electricity for society at a lower LCOE compared to the LCOE of the French grid electricity mix. Considering the best-case and worst-case scenarios regarding the share of RES used by FCC-ee, the benefit under consideration ranges from 227.1 to 194.5 million CHF (or from 117.3 to 100.4 million CHF in discounted values). In the worst-case scenario, the values remain the same as in the baseline because the expected shares of offshore wind used by CERN and made available to society do not change. In the best-case scenario, the share of offshore wind used by CERN increases, reducing the baseload available to society and thus shrinking the benefit.

Table 61: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED
Baseline	117,281,244	227,136,998
Best-case scenario*	100,385,959	194,461,203
Worst-case scenario*	117,281,244	227,136,998

Source: Authors

* These scenarios refer to the share of offshore wind used by CERN. If it increases (as in the best-case scenario), the baseload available to society decreases, thus shrinking the benefit.

5.2. Savings of GHG emissions due to heat recovery

A large part of the energy used to operate the particle collider and its experiments is converted into heat. Traditionally, the heat is dissipated via water-based cooling systems that connect to evaporation towers. A study has been conducted to prove the feasibility of recovering and re-using waste heat. The idea is that the recovered waste heat will be supplied via district heating networks to consumers in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites. The environmental benefit stems from the fact that the energy used by the FCC research infrastructure is re-used and supplied for heating and cooling purposes, avoiding the use of alternative, mainly non-renewable, sources with higher carbon intensity such as gas, wood, oil and conventional electricity mix. Accordingly, the benefit is calculated as the difference between the value of GHG emissions produced by the mix of energy used for heating and cooling purposes in the CERN region and the (lower) GHG emissions in the scenario of the CERN waste heat.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the volumes of CO₂eq savings using FCC waste heat

The table below shows the carbon intensity of the current energy mix used to produce heat in the region around CERN. It is, on average, 186.7 gCO₂e/KWh. A 4% annual reduction in the carbon intensity of the energy mix is envisaged starting in 2025, in line with France’s objective of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. As a result, the grid’s carbon intensity is projected to reach approximately 70 gCO₂e/KWh by 2048 and around 40 gCO₂e/KWh by 2062, the period during which the waste heat is expected to be recovered. The expected carbon intensity of the energy mix for heat production with the FCC is approximately 18 gCO₂e/kWh in the baseline scenario, 17 gCO₂e/kWh in the best-case scenario, and 22 gCO₂e/kWh in the worst-case scenario. The hypotheses on the electricity mix used by FCC are explained in 3.1.1.2.

Table 62: CO₂(eq) intensity for alternative heating systems.

HEATING SYSTEM	gCO ₂ eq/KWH	WEIGHT IN THE ENERGY MIX	WEIGHTED CO ₂ eq PER YEAR gCO ₂ eq/KWH
Electrical heating	147	0.36	52.9
Gas heating	227	0.34	77.2
Oil heating	324	0.16	51.8
Wood (renewable)	30	0.11	3.3
Heat pump	49	0.03	1.5
Total		1.00	186.7

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication. Calculation based on ADEME, Carbone 4 and Pays de Gex Agglomeration

The waste heat supplied as a result of the FCC operation sourced from sustainable energy sources is presented in Section 6.1. Specifically, the estimated yearly potential waste heat consumption in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites over the FCC-ee lifetime, assuming a different consumption potential over the different operation phases of the FCC-ee project, is detailed in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Table 6363 shows the CO₂eq savings from using the FCC waste heat to produce energy as compared to using the current energy mix used to produce heat in the region around CERN. The reduced carbon footprint is calculated for the FCC-ee operational phase only.

Table 63: Volumes of CO₂eq savings using FCC waste heat over the operational phase (tons CO₂eq).

SCENARIO RELATED HEAT TO SUPPLY	SCENARIO RELATED TO ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION		
	Baseline	Best-case	Worst-case
Baseline	173,563	178,318	156,194
Best-case	247,875	254,804	222,525
Worst-case	126,058	129,490	113,529

Source: Authors.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO₂eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal [\[see 7\]](#).⁶⁸ One ton of CO₂eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO₂eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

The environmental benefit of waste heat reuse is derived from the avoided GHG emissions in the project scenario, where CERN supplies waste heat—produced using a cleaner electricity mix—to district heating networks serving consumers near the FCC-ee sites. This is compared to the emissions from alternative heating and cooling methods typically used in the CERN region. Consistently with the negative externality of GHG emissions, the French energy mix is considered in the baseline scenario. **The total benefit is estimated at 169.9 million CHF (undiscounted), corresponding to 74.1 million CHF after discounting.** In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value decreases to 53.9 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it remains about 104.9 million CHF.

Table 64: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED
Baseline	74,056,432	169,958,795
Worst-case	53,931,023	123,405,629
Best-case	104,866,449	242,909,285

Source: Authors

⁶⁸ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see [\[39\]](#) in Reference section.

5.3. Benefits from ecosystem services

Introduction

Along with the construction of necessary infrastructure (buildings, roads) for the FCC, CERN also foresees the implementation of mitigation actions. These action aims to generate positive externalities to compensate for the negative ones associated with the construction of the FCC-ee (presented in Section 3.5). The planned **mitigation actions** (to date) include:

- Creation of green buffers next to the project site with tree planting (15.2 hectares) and meadow creation (6.8 hectares). Data refers to the optimized scenario described in Table 25.
- Improvement and preservation of wetlands within the project's reserved area (7.8 hectares)
- Re-creation of agricultural areas to other locations out of the project's reserved area, in sites to be indicated by host state notified bodies.

The list of mitigation actions is not fully defined, as the implementation of the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach that requires a goal of ecological equivalence (=biodiversity gains at least equal to the biodiversity losses caused by the project) is still ongoing, and it might require additionally environmentally positive measures to be implemented.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantification

The analysis focuses on the most significant expected change in ecosystem services caused by the project's interventions, setting aside the mitigating interventions where the impacted land is relatively small or where the marginal increase in the value of ecosystem services is negligible or difficult to determine⁶⁹. Therefore, the focus is placed on the 7.8 ha of re-naturalization area designated for targeted wetland improvement actions.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The monetisation of ecosystem services gains was conducted by taking the difference of the value of regulating and ecosystem service retrieved from the ESVD database⁷⁰ for wetlands compared to intensive use land/cropland. Regulating and supporting services considered for wetlands include air quality regulation, climate regulation/C-sequestration and moderation of extreme events.

The total regulating & habitat service gain from re-naturalization activities was estimated at 1,582 EUR/ha/year.

⁶⁹ E.g. The tree planted area was discarded as the average metrics available from the ESVD database for temperate forest are hardly applicable to newly planted tree area, assuming that its biodiversity services content will not be the same, especially until trees are not grown

⁷⁰ See Section 5 for additional details on ESVD database

Table 65: Regulating & habitat services gain of wetland improvement (EUR/ha/year)

ECOSYSTEM	UNIT OF MEASURE	VALUE
Inland Wetlands	EUR/ha/year	2,156
Intensive use land/cropland	EUR/ha/year	574
Difference	EUR/ha/year	1,582

Source: Authors based on ESVD data

As mentioned in the case of ecosystem services loss (see Section 5.5), the monetization of these services should be interpreted with prudence, as demonstrated by the high variabilities of metrics from literature and case studies.

Results

The total benefits from ecosystem services gained thanks to re-naturalization activities is estimated at 388,002 CHF undiscounted, equalling 206,971 CHF discounted, obtained by multiplying the EUR 1,582 ecosystem services gain to the total hectares impacted by re-naturalization activities starting from the year 2032, assuming that these activities are conducted in parallel with construction works.

Table 66: Total estimation -baseline scenario (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL DISCOUNTED	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED
Baseline	206,971	388,002

Source: Authors

6. LOCAL IMPACTS

6.1. Reuse of waste heat

Introduction

A large part of the energy used to operate the particle collider and its experiments is converted into heat. The heat is dissipated via water-based cooling systems that connect to evaporation towers. A study has been conducted to prove the feasibility of recovering and re-using waste heat. The idea is that the recovered waste heat will be supplied via district heating networks to consumers in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites. The benefit considered in this section is the avoided cost of purchasing energy for heating and air conditioning from conventional energy sources such as oil, wood, gas and electricity, thanks to the fact that the price of the heat supplied by the CERN sources is lower than the one produced by conventional energy sources. The environmental benefits associated with the reuse of heat are discussed in section 3.2.1.

It is worth noting that the reuse of waste heat also results in slight energy and water savings compared to a scenario without such a system (see box). However, these savings are already factored into the quantities of energy and water considered in the analysis, as well as their associated costs. Since the counterfactual scenario in the analysis assumes the absence of an FCC altogether, the energy and water savings from the reuse of waste heat do not generate a net benefit but rather contribute to a reduced cost for energy and water.

Box 6: Energy and water savings due to waste heat re-use

In particle accelerators, cooling systems use large amounts of water to dissipate the heat generated by equipment. This water is often evaporated in cooling towers, leading to significant water consumption. However, by distributing waste heat for other uses, such as heating nearby buildings or industrial processes, less water is needed for cooling. This reduction in evaporation helps save water, which was estimated by experts at CERN to be approximately 1.6 cubic meters of water being saved per megawatt-hour (MWh) of heat distributed.

Moreover, by distributing waste heat for other uses, some cooling towers will no longer be needed or will operate at reduced capacity. This reduces the energy consumption associated with cooling, as less energy will be required to run these systems. The experts at CERN have estimated that the energy savings might be around 4000 MWh on average per year. It is considered to be 0 for the long shutdown year.

Source: Authors processing of CERN communication

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Estimation of the amount of waste heat recovered

The table below shows the waste heat capacities per year from the various sources in the FCC-ee machine (magnets, alcoves, absorbers, experiments, power convertors, RF, cryogenics, general services, and chilled water). The total anticipated heat production varies from approximately 830 GWh during the operational Z phase to about 1,600 GWh during the operational tt phase (excluding the long shutdown phase). Based on these assumptions, a significant amount of heat can be recovered, particularly at the PH site in Cercier/Marlioiz, France, due to the presence of the

superconducting radiofrequency particle acceleration system. In contrast, the potential is relatively lower for the PB (Presinge/Choulex) and PF (Éteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron) sites.

Table 67: Waste heat production per year and per FCC-ee operational phase (MWh).

BEAM ENERGY À	45.6 GEV	80 GEV	120 GEV	182.5 GEV
Operation mode	Z	W	H	tt
Heat energy produced	MWh	MWh	MWh	MWh
Site PA	137 898	151 852	172 485	225 289
Site PB	14 890	17 726	22 788	34 419
Site PD	137 898	151 852	172 485	225 289
Site PF	14 890	17 726	22 788	34 419
Site PG	137 898	151 852	172 485	225 289
Site PH	229 602	313 584	335 949	523 762
Site PJ	137 898	151 852	172 485	225 289
Site PL	24 894	48 215	56 380	109 157
Total per year	835,868	1,004,659	1,127,845	1,602,913

Source: CERN communication and Ginger-Burgeap

➤ **STEP 2 – Estimation of demand for waste heat**

FCC-ee can provide stable waste heat over long periods during the year. Potential consumers have been identified within a 5 km radius. The estimated yearly potential waste heat consumption has been distributed over the FCC-ee lifetime, assuming a different consumption potential over the different operation phases of the FCC-ee project, as detailed in **Error! Reference source not found.**³⁶.

Table 68: Waste heat quantity and potential consumption by FCC-ee phase and site (GWh/year)

MODE	Z			W			H			TT		
Baseline												
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%
PA	137.9	137.9	100	151.9	150.0	100	172.5	169.0	98	225.3	212.0	94
PB	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.7	100	22.8	22.8	100	34.4	34.0	99
PD	137.9	45.0	32	151.9	46.0	30	172.5	46.0	26	225.3	49.0	22
PF	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.0	96	22.8	21.0	92	34.4	29.0	84
PG	137.9	40.0	29	151.9	40.0	26	172.5	40.0	23	225.3	40.0	18
PH	229.6	6.0	3	313.6	6.0	2	335.9	6.0	2	523.8	7.0	1
PJ	137.9	20.0	15	151.9	20.0	13	172.5	20.0	12	225.3	20.0	9
PL	24.9	19.0	76	48.2	30.0	62	56.4	32.0	57	109.2	33.0	30
Total	835.8	297.8	36	1004.8	326.7	32	1128	356.8	32	1603	424.0	26
Worst-case scenario												
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%
PA	137.9	122.0	87	151.9	130.0	86	172.5	139.0	81	225.3	161.0	71
PB	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.7	100	22.8	23.0	100	34.4	34.0	99
PD	137.9	25.0	10	151.9	26.0	11	172.5	26.0	15	225.3	26.0	12
PF	14.9	12.0	80	17.7	13.0	73	22.8	15.0	66	34.4	19.0	55
PG	137.9	23.0	17	151.9	24.0	16	172.5	24.0	14	225.3	24.0	11
PH	229.6	6.0	3	313.6	6.0	2	335.9	6.0	2	523.8	7.0	1
PJ	137.9	11.0	8	151.9	12.0	8	172.5	12.0	7	225.3	13.0	58
PL	24.9	9.0	36	48.2	10.0	21	56.4	11.0	20	109.2	11.0	10
Total	835.8	222.9	27	1004.8	238.7	24	1128	256.0	23	1603	295.0	18
Best-case scenario												
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%
PA	137.9	162.8	122	151.9	200.1	131	172.5	228.8	132	225.3	334.4	148
PB	14.9	152.8	1025	17.7	169.6	958	22.8	195.3	856	34.4	259.7	755
PD	137.9	-	-	151.9	-	-	172.5	-	-	225.3	-	-
PF	14.9	15.0	100	17.7	17.0	100	22.8	21.07	92	34.4	29.0	84
PG	137.9	40.0	29	151.9	40.0	26	172.5	40.0	23	225.3	40.0	18
PH	229.6	-	-	313.6	-	?	335.9	-	-	523.8	-	-
PJ	137.9	20.0	15	151.9	20.0	13	172.5	20.0	12	225.3	20.0	9
PL	24.9	-	-	48.2	-	-	56.4	-	-	109.2	-	-
Total	835.8	390.6	47	1004.8	446.6	44	1128	505.1	45	1603	683.2	43

Source: CERN communication and Ginger-Burgeap, 2024

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimation of the avoided cost**

The cost for the supply of waste heat in a district for heating and air conditioning (cooling) purposes (C) is given by the cost for the service (S) and the cost of energy (E): $C = S + E$. These components depend on the mix of sources used to obtain heat (gas, electricity, etc.). More specifically:

- S includes transport and distribution costs, management costs (investment and operation costs), marketing costs and the supplier's earnings margin.
- E is the cost of energy.

The table below shows the cost of waste heat considering the heating (and cooling) cost per year of an apartment between 50 and 100 m² in the region around CERN. The typical heating consumption for a 50 m² apartment is 6 MWh per year, so the working hypothesis is a consumption per year of 10 MWh per year per apartment/household. It compares the costs in three cases:

- Heat is distributed via a network fuelled by gas.
- Heat is distributed via a network fuelled by electricity.
- Heat is distributed via a network using the FCC-ee waste heat.

Table 69: Cost for the supply of waste heat and avoided cost (EUR/MWh and CHF/MWh).

	COST OF THE SERVICE (S)	COST OF ENERGY (E)	TOTAL COST (EUR/MWH)	NOTE
Gas	26	103	129	
Electricity	129*	219	219	*It is assumed that the cost of the service does not apply since every household typically has a general electricity supply contract, even if the electricity is not used for heating purposes.
FCC-ee waste heat	108	2*	110	*As regards the cost of energy, CERN only receives 2 EUR/MWh from the heat network operator to compensate for the creation of the infrastructure to supply heat within CERN premises.
AVOIDED COSTS		EUR/MWH	CHF/MWH	NOTE
FCC waste heat vs. gas		19	18	
FCC waste heat vs. electricity		109	104	
FCC waste heat vs. a mix of gas and electricity		64	61	A simple average between the gas and electricity prices is considered.

Source: CERN communication and Ginger-Burgeap, 2024.

Results

When multiplying the avoided cost from using the CERN waste heat as compared to the mix of gas and electricity with the yearly demand in the baseline scenario, a total of 312.6 million CHF of benefit is estimated over the project time horizon, corresponding to 131.9 million CHF in discounted terms. In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value decreases to 95.4 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it increases to 264.0 million CHF.

Table 70: Total estimation – under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED	TOTAL DISCOUNTED
Baseline	312,578,794	131,944,519
Worst-case scenario	225,392,886	95,445,971
Best-case scenario	456,574,149	263,985,401

Source: Authors.

6.2. Value of Emergency Services

A larger accelerator like the FCC requires a new emergency preparedness and intervention framework supported by infrastructure at both underground and surface levels. As part of this safety concept, the transition of emergency and fire brigade services from CERN to a financial and training support scheme with regional services is planned. In response to local department requests, these activities are expected to involve a total commitment of 1,925 person-years from 2029 until the end of decommissioning in 2069.

The economic value of firefighters in the region is estimated by multiplying the number of personnel by the yearly value of one firefighter, calculated using the hourly rate of voluntary work (€35.61 in 2021 prices) and the average annual intervention hours (91). This results in an approximate total of €7 million (undiscounted). Additionally, the cost of materials—including vehicles, heavy transport, equipment, and training—is estimated at €32 million (undiscounted) over the same period.

After converting and discounting these values to reflect current prices, the final figures are expressed in CHF (see Table below).

Table 71: Total estimation – baseline scenario (CHF, 2024).

SCENARIO	TOTAL UNDISCOUNTED	TOTAL DISCOUNTED
Baseline	30,132,367	15,777,497

Source: Authors

7. REFERENCES

- [1] CSIL, & European Organization for Nuclear Research, (February 13, 2024) Socio-economic impacts of the lepton collider-based research infrastructure (V01.00) <https://zenodo.org/records/10653396>
- [2] Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024). The Link Between Large Scientific Collaboration and Productivity. Rethinking How to Estimate the Monetary Value of Publications. arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.10278.
- [3] Florio, M., Forte, S., & Sirtori, E. (2016). Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider: A cost-benefit analysis to 2025 and beyond. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, 38-53.
- [4] Bianchin, C., Giacomelli, P., Iconomidou-Fayard, L., Niedziela, J., and Sciascia, B. (2019). Study on the career trajectories of people with a working experience at CERN. CERN Yellow Reports: Monographs, CERN-2019-004. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2689210/files/90-78-PB.pdf>
- [5] Bastianin, A., Del Bo, C. F., Florio, M., & Giffoni, F. (2022). Projecting the socio-economic impact of a big science center: the world's largest particle accelerator at CERN. *Applied Economics*, 55(49), 5768-5789. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2022.2140763>.
- [6] European Commission, (2014). Guide to cost-benefit analysis of investment projects. Economic appraisal tool for Cohesion Policy, 2014-2020, Directorate for Regional Policy, authored by Sartori, D., Catalano, G., Genco, M., Pancotti, C., Sirtori, E., Vignetti, S., & Del Bo, C.
- [7] European Commission (2021). Economic Appraisal Vademecum 2021-2027, prepared by DG REGIO with the support of JASPERS experts involved in project economic appraisal, Lead Author: Sartori, D., https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/newsroom/news/2021/09/20-09-2021-project-selection-the-economic-appraisal-vademecum
- [8] Bastianin and Florio (2018). Social Cost Benefit Analysis of HL-LHC. Cern report, CERN-ACC-2018-0014. Available here: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2319300/files/CERN-ACC-2018-0014.pdf> Last access on 24.01.2025
- [9] Morretta, V., Vurchio, D., & Carrazza, S. (2022). The socio-economic value of scientific publications: The case of Earth Observation satellites. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 180, 121730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121730>.
- [10] Florio, M., and Sirtori, E. (2016). Social benefits and costs of large scale research infrastructures. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, pp.65-78.
- [11] Catalano, G. (2024). Thinking How to Define and Measure Impacts of RIs. In *The Economics of Big Science 2.0: Essays by Leading Scientists and Policymakers* (pp. 109-126). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- [12] Griniece, E., Angelis, J., Reid A, Vignetti, S., Catalano, J., Helman, A., Barberis Rami, M. (2020), Guidebook for socio-economic impact assessment of research infrastructures, https://ri-paths.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/D5.4_RI-PATHS_Guidebook.pdf
- [13] Camporesi, T. (2001). High-energy physics as a career springboard. *European Journal of Physics*, 22(2), 139-148.

- [14] Camporesi, T., Catalano, G., Florio, M., and Giffoni, F. (2017). Experiential learning in high energy physics: a survey of students at the LHC. *European Journal of Physics*, 025703 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6404/aa5121>
- [15] Catalano, G., Giffoni, F., & Morretta, V. (2021). Human and social capital accumulation within research infrastructures: The case of CERN. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12317>
- [16] Castelnovo, P., Florio, M., Forte, S., Rossi, L., & Sirtori, E. (2018). The economic impact of technological procurement for large-scale research infrastructures: Evidence from the Large Hadron Collider at CERN. *Research Policy*, 47(9), 1853-1867.
- [17] Bianchi-Streit, M., R. Blackburne, R. Budde, H. Reitz, B. Sagnell, H. Schmied and B. Schorr (1984), 'Economic Utility Resulting from Cern Contracts: (Second Study),' CERN Paper, 84-14, Geneva.
- [18] Schmied, H. (1977), 'A study of economic utility resulting from CERN contracts,' *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, EM-24(4),125–138.
- [19] CERN. (2023). CERN Environment Report—Rapport sur l'environnement 2021–2022. <https://doi.org/10.25325/CERN-Environment-2023-003>
- [20] S. Andresz, T. Jobert and C. Schieber (2022). The evolution of the reference monetary value of the man.sievert at Électricité de France, *Radioprotection*, 57 4 (2022) 339-345, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/radiopro/2022028>
- [21] Meurisse, B., Robinet, A., Hartmann, L., Ni, J., Dervaux, B., & Rochaix, L., Le coût des nuisances sonores des chantiers: quelle intégration dans les évaluations socio-économiques de projets?, Commissariat général au développement durable, France Stratégie, Secrétariat général pour l'investissement, 2022.
- [22] European Commission: Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport, Essen, H., Fiorello, D., El Beyrouty, K., Bieler, C. et al., *Handbook on the external costs of transport – Version 2019 – 1.1*, Publications Office, 2020.
- [23] DEFRA: Interdepartmental Group on Costs and Benefits (IGCB(N)), Muirhead, M., Dickens, R., Angulo, M., Turner, S., Gill, J., Abdul, M., Hirani, H., *Environmental Noise: Valuing Impacts on Sleep Disturbance, Annoyance, Hypertension, Productivity, and Quiet*, Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs,2014.
- [24] Commissariat Général à la Stratégie et à la Prospective (CGSP), Quinet, É., Baumstark, L., Bonnet, J., Croq, A., Ducos, G., Meunier, D., Rigard-Cerison, A., Roquigny, Q., *Évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics – Rapport final*, CGSP, 2013.
- [25] Bernard Chevassus-Au-Louis, Jean-Michel Salles, Jean-Luc Pujol, Sabine Bielsa, Gilles Martin, et al *Approche économique de la biodiversité et des services liés aux écosystèmes : contribution à la décision publique. [Rapport Technique]* Ministère de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la Pêche. 2009.
- [26] Ministère de l'Économie, des Finances et de la Relance - Direction Générale du Trésor, *Évaluations économiques des services rendus par la biodiversité*, 2021
- [27] *The Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB*, 2nd edition, March 2023.
- [28] *Cost–Benefit Analysis and the Environment: Further developments and policy use*, OECD, 2018.

- [29] Compensations environnementale, forestière et collective agricole: évaluation et mise en cohérence, Rapport CGEDD n° 013246-01, March 2021.
- [30] Markandya, A. (2016), Cost Benefit Analysis and the Environment: How to best cover impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services, OECD environment working papers No. 101, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- [31] Integrating Ecosystem Values into Cost-Benefit Analysis: Recommendations for USAID and Practitioners, 2018.
- [32] RTE (2022) Futurs énergétiques 2050.
- [33] Trinomics 2020 Final Report – LCOE & LCOH: Energy costs, taxes and the impact of government interventions on investments. On behalf of DG ENER.
- [34] Stratégie, F., 2019. *La valeur de l'action pour le climat*, France Stratégie. France.
- [35] Gruber, Jonathan (2011). "Chapter 8: Cost–Benefit Analysis", Public Finance and Public Policy, 3rd edition, ISBN-13: 978-1-4292-1949-5, pp. 209–210 and 220-221, online available at <https://www.coursesidekick.com/economics/653961>.
- [36] Zhuang, L., Liang, Z., Lin, T. and De Guzman, F. (2007). Theory and practice in the choice of social discount rate for cost benefit analysis: A survey, ERD Working Paper n° 94, Asian Development Bank
- [37] Lopez, H. (2008). The social discount rate: estimates for nine Latin American countries. The World Bank.
- [38] Catalano G. and Pancotti C. (2021). The social discount rates: recent estimations in selected countries. CSIL working paper, forthcoming.
- [39] France Stratégie (2019), *La valeur de l'action pour le climat: Une valeur tutélaire du carbone pour évaluer les investissements et les politiques publiques*.
- [40] IAEA (2024) Approaches to Cost-Benefit Analysis of New Nuclear Power Projects, IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NG-T-4.8, IAEA, Vienna (2024), <https://doi.org/10.61092/iaea.5t26-8tpd>
- CERN: various personal communications to the team as stored in CERNbox

Further sources

- Bastianin, A., & Florio, M. (2023), The socioeconomic impact of large scale research infrastructures: models, methods, and data. In *Big Science in the 21st Century: Economic and societal impacts* (pp. 16-1). Bristol, UK: IOP Publishing.
- Bastianin, A., Castelnovo, P., Florio, M., Giunta, A. (2021). Big science and innovation: gestation lag from procurement to patents for CERN suppliers. *J Technol Transf* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-021-09854-5>
- Battistoni, G., Genco, M., Marsilio, M., Pancotti, C., Rossi, S., & Vignetti, S. (2016). Cost–benefit analysis of applied research infrastructure. Evidence from health care. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, 79-91.
- Carrazza, S., Ferrara, A., and Salini, S. (2016). Research infrastructures in the LHC era: A scientometric approach. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, pp. 121-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.02.005>

- Catalano, G., Castelnovo, P., Landoni, M., Giffoni, F. (2023), "The outcomes of public procurements: an empirical analysis of the Italian space industry", *J Technol Transf*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-023-10038-6>.
- Catalano, G., Delugas, E., & Vignetti, S. (2024). Costs and Benefits of Open Science: Contributing to the Development of a Rigorous Assessment Framework. In *The Economics of Big Science 2.0: Essays by Leading Scientists and Policymakers* (pp. 127-135). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Florio, M, and Giffoni, F. (2020). 'A contingent valuation experiment about future particle accelerators at CERN', *PLoS ONE*, vol. 15(3): e0229885. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229885>
- Florio, M. (2014). *Applied Welfare Economics: cost-benefit analysis of projects and policies*. Routledge, New York. ISBN: 978-0-415-85833-5
- Florio, M. (2019). *Investing in science: Social cost-benefit analysis of research infrastructures*. MIT Press.
- Florio, M. and Sirtori, E. (2013). *The Social Cost of Capital: Recent Estimates for the EU Countries*. Centre for Industrial Studies Working Paper 03, Milan, Italy.
- Florio, M. Bastianin, A., Castelnovo, P., Giunta, A. (2019), *Technological Learning and Innovation Gestation Lags at the Frontier of Science: from CERN Procurement to Patent*, Working papers 1905.09552, [arXiv.org](https://arxiv.org), <https://ideas.repec.org/p/mib/wpaper/405.html>, currently submitted.
- Florio, M., & Giffoni, F. (2019), *The societal impacts of big science: how to manage it? (L'impatto sociale della produzione di scienza su larga scala: come governarlo?)*, in *L'industria*, 40(4), 661-692, <https://www.rivisteweb.it/doi/10.1430/95936>.
- Florio, M., & Pancotti, C. (2020), *The Economics of Physics: The Social Cost-Benefit Analysis of Large Research Infrastructures*. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Physics*.
- Florio, M., Forte, S., Pancotti, C., Sirtori, E., & Vignetti, S. (2016). *Exploring Cost-Benefit Analysis of Research, Development and Innovation Infrastructures: An Evaluation Framework* working paper 01/2016, CSIL Centre for Industrial Studies, Corso Monforte, 15, 20122 Milano MI, Italy (March, 2016). [arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.03654](https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.03654).
- Florio, M., Giffoni, F., Giunta, A. and Sirtori, E. (2018). *Big Science, Learning and Innovation: Evidence from CERN Procurement*. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, Volume 27, Issue 5, 915–936.
- Morretta, V., Florio, M., & Landoni, M. (2023), *The social value of Earth Observation: a new evaluation framework for public high-tech infrastructures*. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*.
- Vignetti, S. (2021). *Designing a Research Infrastructure with Impact in Mind*. In *The Economics of Big Science* (pp. 79-84). Springer, Cham.

8. ANNEXES

8.1. Exchange rates adopted in the socio-economic benefits study

Table 72: Exchange rates adopted in the socio-economic benefits study

CURRENCIES (EUR VS OTHERS): ES. 1 EUR = X AMOUNT OF THE CORRESPONDING CURRENCY	AVERAGE 2024	CURRENCIES (CHF VS OTHERS): ES. 1 CHF = X AMOUNT OF THE CORRESPONDING CURRENCY	AVERAGE 2024
EUR VS USD (US DOLLAR)	1.08	CHF VS USD (US DOLLAR)	1.14
EUR VS GBP (BRITISH POUND)	0.85	CHF VS GBP (BRITISH POUND)	0.89
EUR VS INR (INDIAN RUPEE)	90.56	CHF VS INR (INDIAN RUPEE)	95.06
EUR VS BRL (BRAZILIAN REAL)	5.83	CHF VS BRL (BRAZILIAN REAL)	6.12
EUR VS CAD (CANADIAN DOLLAR)	1.48	CHF VS CAD (CANADIAN DOLLAR)	1.56
EUR VS CNY (CHINESE YUAN)	7.79	CHF VS CNY (CHINESE YUAN)	8.17
EUR VS PLN (POLISH ZLOTY)	4.31	CHF VS PLN (POLISH ZLOTY)	4.52
EUR VS CHF (SWISS FRANC)	0.95	CHF VS CHF (SWISS FRANC)	1.00
EUR VS AUD (AUSTRALIAN DOLLAR)	1.64	CHF VS AUD (AUSTRALIAN DOLLAR)	1.72
EUR VS SEK (SWEDISH KRONA)	11.43	CHF VS SEK (SWEDISH KRONA)	12.00
EUR VS JPY (JAPANESE YEN)	163.85	CHF VS JPY (JAPANESE YEN)	172.00
EUR VS CZK (CZECH KORUNA)	25.12	CHF VS CZK (CZECH KORUNA)	26.37
EUR VS DKK (DANISH KRONE)	7.46	CHF VS DKK (DANISH KRONE)	7.83
EUR VS ILS (ISRAELI SHEKEL)	4.01	CHF VS ILS (ISRAELI SHEKEL)	4.21
EUR VS COP (PESO COLOMBIANO)	4403.67	CHF VS COP (PESO COLOMBIANO)	4622.79
EUR VS AMD (ARMENIAN DRAM)	395.17	CHF VS AMD (ARMENIAN DRAM)	414.83
EUR VS HUF (HUNGARIAN FORINT)	395.30	CHF VS HUF (HUNGARIAN FORINT)	414.97
EUR VS THB (THAI BAHT)	38.18	CHF VS THB (THAI BAHT)	40.08

Source: Authors

8.2. Approach and estimates for the SDR

The SDR allows assigning one monetary figure of costs and benefits that occur over time using a mathematical expression that is valid at one specific point in time. This process is called "discounting", and the resulting value is called the "present value". The formula is:

$$\text{Present Value of Benefit } B = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{B_t}{(1 + \text{SDR})^t}$$

where:

- t is one year of the observation period, running from 1 (first year of the analysis) to n (end of the observation period)
- B_t is the value of benefit B at time t
- SDR is the social discount rate value established for the analysis.

The SDR reflects how society values well-being today versus well-being in the future. This has important implications for resource allocation in investment projects. The proper discount rate should represent the opportunity cost of what else could be accomplished with those same funds⁷¹. Relatively higher SDR values reflect the fact that people have preferences for consuming resources today instead of investing them and thus postponing consumption in the future (the present value decreases quickly and reflects the fact that it is not attractive for people to make long-term investments). In this case, society prefers to increase welfare now rather than later through increased consumption. Relatively lower SDR values indicate that society is more ready to renounce part of its consumption today in favour of investing it for future benefits since the values will decrease slower. A zero SDR means that society has no time preferences in choosing between present and future consumption. In general, though, people tend to prefer to consume immediately to be able to profit from their investments today rather than later because there is less probability in the future to be able to profit from the investments (e.g. due to life expectancy or the risk of emerging crises and economic downturns). However, without investments no benefits would be possible at all in the future. Hence, a preference-stated equilibrium that is determined by external factors occurs, which applies to a particular socio-economic environment at a particular point in time. The SDR changes, therefore, over time as the preference of the society changes with evolving socio-economic boundary conditions (e.g. economic growth, recession, peace and war times, health and life-expectation or health crises such as the pandemic, accelerating or decelerating climate change, technological breakthroughs, trust, and distrust in the future).

Empirical evidence from the economic literature⁷² shows that the SDR is higher in developing countries (a preference to profit from investments immediately), often characterised by a higher GDP growth rate, than in countries with more mature economic systems, where people are more willing to invest in the future since it is more stable and predictable and since their life expectancy is higher⁷³.

⁷¹ See [35] in Reference section

⁷² See for instance [36 and 37].

⁷³ In line with this argument, and to mention one example of SDR estimated for the period 2014-2020, [6] recommended that a 5% SDR is used for the appraisal of major investment projects in the Cohesion countries (EU Member States with a lower GDP level) and a 3% SDR for the other EU Member States.

SDR values can be estimated with different methods⁷⁴. One of the most common methods used by international organisations is based on the social rate of time preference (SRTP)⁷⁵, which considers the social preferences and welfare of both current and future generations. [The SRTP captures three aspects for determining the discounting factor:](#)

- i. The pure [time preference of consumers](#): consumers prefer to receive the same amount of goods and services sooner rather than later.
- ii. The [assumption of a steadily increasing level of income and consumption for society](#).
- iii. The [opportunity cost of resources](#): the allocation of any type of resource (money, persons, time) to a project represents a lost opportunity for society since the funds could have been spent on other, potentially more beneficial investments.

For this analysis, the SDR is set according to the SRTP approach with the following formula:

$$SDR = SRTP = p + \varepsilon * g$$

where:

- *p* is the *pure time preference*. It captures the impatience and myopia of people to consume as soon as possible instead of delaying consumption to the future. It can be proxied with the annual mortality rate of the population, assuming that consumption is anticipated when the risk of death or human race extinction increases. For the purpose of calculation, we used the [average crude death rate over the period 2022-2041 provided by Eurostat. Where missing, the World Bank value for 2021-2040 was used as an alternative](#)
- *ε* is the *elasticity of marginal utility of consumption*. This parameter measures the extent to which the satisfaction (utility) from additional consumption decreases as the level of consumption rises. When the current level of consumption provides “saturation”, increasing consumption even more would still provide satisfaction but to a lower extent. Assuming there is some growth ($g > 0$), consumption has a lower unit utility in the future. The term ($\varepsilon * g$) will still be positive, but ε decreases as g increases. There are several methods to estimate ε . The most common ones are those based on (progressivity of) taxation models, which influence people’s demand for goods and services: as income increases, taxes increase more than proportionally, and available income for consumption decreases. We estimate the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption based on social preferences revealed by taxation. [We used the 2022 OECD Taxation Database to determine ε. When data was not available, the value was estimated through value transfer \(average between the regression and ML estimate considering data for 2000-2019\).](#)
- *g* is the expected per-capita growth rate of consumption. It is proxied by the real growth rate of the per-capita GDP under the assumption that the GDP properly reflects the dynamics of consumption over time. For the purpose of calculation, [we used the expected per capita GDP](#)

⁷⁴ The social rate of return on private investments (SRRI), the social rate of time preference (SRTP), the weighted average approach (WAA), the shadow price of capital. See [\[6\]](#) for details. Moreover, a more detailed explanation of the rationale for using the SDR as well as of the different approaches for calculating it is reported in [\[38\]](#).

⁷⁵ The theoretical foundation of the SRTP is the Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model or Ramsey growth model (Ramsey, 1928; Cass, 1965; Koopmans, 1965). It is a neoclassical model of economic growth based primarily on the work of Ramsey (1928). According to the model, there is a social planner (the government) that solves an inter-temporal optimization problem of social utility with respect to consumption, considering the welfare of both current and future generations. The Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model differs from the Solow–Swan (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956) model in that the choice of consumption is explicitly micro founded at a point in time and so endogenizes the savings rate.

growth rate over the period 2021-2042 calculated on the basis of data provided by OECD. When data were missing, the past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the World Bank was used as an alternative.

By applying the formula above, we estimated the SDR in each country that contributes to the CERN budget today, including CERN member states and Associated Countries⁷⁶. We then estimated the average of the SDR in each country, weighted by the respective contribution to the CERN budget. The table below shows the data entering into the calculation along with the estimated SDR for each country and the weighted average value used for the socio-economic impacts assessment of the FCC-ee.

Table 73: Data entering the SDR calculation

COUNTRY	P - EXPECTED DEATH RATE (EUROSTAT, 2022-2041)	E (OECD 2022)	G - EXPECTED PER CAPITA GDP GROWTH RATE (2021-2042)	UNWEIGHTED SDR	% CONTRIBUTION TO THE CERN BUDGET (2024)
CERN Member States					
Austria	0.88	1.63	0.88	2.47	2.2%
Belgium	1.02	1.78	1.02	2.82	2.7%
Bulgaria	1.90	1.00	1.90	3.47	0.4%
Czechia	1.59	1.39	1.59	3.40	1.2%
Denmark	1.00	1.23	1.00	2.29	1.8%
Finland	1.18	1.69	1.18	3.15	1.3%
France	1.01	1.69	1.01	2.70	13.1%
Germany	0.81	1.45	0.81	2.38	20.6%
Greece	1.54	1.63	1.54	3.77	1.0%
Hungary	1.68	1.00	1.68	3.05	0.7%
Israel	1.38	1.82	1.38	3.04	2.2%
Italy	0.82	2.10	0.82	2.93	9.6%
Netherlands	0.90	1.85	0.90	2.68	4.6%
Norway	0.88	1.78	0.88	2.44	2.1%
Poland	1.88	1.28	1.88	3.62	3.0%
Portugal	1.31	1.52	1.31	3.21	1.1%
Romania	2.18	1.00	2.18	3.58	1.3%
Serbia	3.72*	1.32**	3.72***	6.44	0.3%
Slovakia	1.67	1.28	1.67	3.28	0.5%
Spain	1.15	1.63	1.15	2.86	6.8%
Sweden	1.05	1.46	1.05	2.49	2.6%
Switzerland	0.93	1.61	0.93	2.40	3.7%
UK	0.95	1.47	0.95	2.36	14.7%

⁷⁶ Final Budget of the Organisation for the seventieth financial year 2024, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2888205>

Associate Member States in the pre-stage to Membership

Cyprus	1.38*	1.40**	1.38***	2.75	0.1%
Estonia	2.07	1.93	2.07	5.22	0.1%
Slovenia	1.30	1.35	1.30	2.89	0.2%
Associate Member States					
Croatia	2.68*	1.29**	2.68***	4.87	0.1%
India	4.20	1.44**	4.20	6.83	1.4%
Latvia	2.05	1.40	2.05	4.40	0.1%
Lithuania	1.86	1.22	1.86	3.69	0.1%
Pakistan	2.41*	1.46**	2.41***	4.18	0.2%
Türkiye	2.57	1.61	2.57	4.74	0.4%
Ukraine	1.328*	1.34**	1.32***	3.41	0.1%
Weighted average SDR	2.8			100%	

Source: Authors **Note:** * World Bank value for 2021-2040 ** value estimated through value transfer *** Past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the World Bank was used as an alternative.